

CODING INSTRUMENTAL GESTURES

Towards a quantitative description
of instrumental gestures
in excitation-continuous musical instruments

by

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Abstract

The subject of this work is the exploration of methods for the characterization of instrumental gestures in music performance. More concretely, we face the case of excitation-continuous monophonic musical instruments. Instrumental gestures are understood here as the actions applied by a musician to produce the sound conveying the musical message contained in the piece or composition being performed. These actions have been measured either from the recorded audio or from physical movement measurements. After surveying some relevant research carried out in the field of instrumental gesture analysis in music performance, as well as the control techniques applied in some of state-of-the-art synthesis trends, we propose some approaches for describing quantitatively instrumental gestures as temporal contours of variables belonging to both the sound domain and the physical action domain, with the final aim of improving existing synthesis methods and opening new ways of gestural synthesis.

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*"One becomes great by what one reads
and not by what one writes"*

J. L. Borges

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Context

1.1.1 The author

In 2000, I got graduated in BSc Electronics Engineering, by Escola Universitària d'Enginyeria Tècnica Industrial de Terrassa (EUETIT), Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC), Barcelona (Spain). Then, I moved to the Escola Tècnica Superior d'Enginyeria de Telecomunicació de Barcelona (ETSETB), Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC), Barcelona (Spain), where I got MSc Electronics Engineering in the year 2003. By the end of my MSc graduation, I got a scholarship from Philips Research in Aachen (Germany), where I worked in a research project dealing with resonant power conversion. My contributions let me write there my Master Thesis, entitled 'Resonant Power Converter for Large Flat Displays', and also to get enrolled in the Department of Electronics of the Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC) (where I worked as an assistant teacher for two years).

My interests in music since I was a child (I had not formal music education) kept me always close to it, self-learning in the keyboards playing and the use of early computer music sequencers. Two years ago, I enrolled the PhD Program in Computer Science and Digital Communication of the Universitat Pompeu Fabra, Barcelona (Spain) as a consequence of the intentions of bringing together my interests in musical applications and academic research.

1.1.2 The Music Technology Group

The Music Technology Group, MTG, part of the Department of Technology and the Audiovisual Institute of the University Pompeu Fabra of Barcelona, specializes in audio processing technologies and their music and multimedia applications. With more than 40 researchers coming from various disciplines, the MTG carries out research and development projects in areas such as audio processing and synthesis; audio identification; audio content analysis, description and transformation; singing voice processing; interactive systems; and software tools. The MTG wants to contribute to the improvement of the technologies of musical interest, carrying out competitive research at the international level and transferring its results to the society. It aims to find a balance between basic and applied research and at the same time to promote interdisciplinary research that incorporates knowledge from both scientific/technological and humanistic/artistic disciplines. The MTG was created in 1994 by its current director, Dr. Xavier Serra, as one of the research groups of the Audiovisual Institute, a centre for interdisciplinary research in the different areas of Digital Media.

Among the different projects/areas in which the MTG is currently involved, we must point out (1) a couple of research projects and (2) a working group because of both their relation with the topic of this work, and my implication in the research carried out. The first project is the "prOmusic" project, a research project dealing with expressive performance modeling by means of inductive machine learning techniques. The second project, just kicked-off and called "Gestural synthesis of violin performance", will deal with the analysis of instrumental gestures in violin performance for controlling a breakthrough sample-based synthesizer based on spectral models. As a working team belonging to the MTG, we also introduce the "Voice and Audio Processing Team" of the MTG due to their work on singing voice synthesis.

The prOmusic project

The aim of prOmusic is to model, using inductive machine learning, the knowledge applied by a musician when performing a score in order to produce an expressive performance of a piece. There are interests in inducing both models for generating and models for explaining expressive music performance. The re-

search involves (a) the extraction of melodic acoustic features from audio recordings that are related to expressivity, (b) the design and application of machine learning algorithms to the extracted features, and (c) the development of expressive synthesis tools for generating expressive output (both MIDI and audio).

I have been involved in the prOmusic project for the last two years, mainly in the analysis and synthesis stages, by getting a description of dynamics and articulation of saxophone jazz recordings for being used in the study of expressive music performance. My research contributions to this project will be presented in Chapter 3.

Gestural Synthesis of Violin Performance

The objective of this project on violin synthesis is to develop a model that translates the input musical score to physical action parameters involved in the sound production during performance. This model will be used in a new-concept sample-based synthesizer in which the physical action parameters of the performer in each context are taken into account during the selection and transformation of samples from the database. In this project, strategies of measuring the physical actions during performance will be studied, as well as the way of correlate them to sound perceptual features and extract some transformation templates during the synthesis stage.

My contributions to this project will stay at the analysis of performance instrumental gestures by means of treating the physical actions applied to the instrument as continuous contours. Audio perceptual features will be also considered. The aim will be the obtaining a flexible and compact representation of the contours that allows modeling and mapping between the domains of physical actions and perceptual features.

The Voice and Audio Processing Team of the MTG

The main research activities of the Voice and Audio Processing Team, in which I am engaged, are spectral processing of sound, singing voice synthesis, singing voice performance analysis, and voice transformations. One of the first projects was to develop a specific spectral based model for the processing of the singing voice. Since then it has been carried out quite a bit of research in this area

and it has been developed a number of systems for the real-time processing and synthesis of the singing voice, including a real-time system for morphing two voices in the context of karaoke, singing voice synthesis, audio time scaling in the context of professional post-production, voice transformations, etc.

In terms of the possible contributions of my research to the activities carried out in this group, it is remarkable the improvements on the expression of singing voice synthesis, thanks to the characterization of perceptual audio features, mainly amplitude and fundamental frequency, but open to the study of other high-level descriptors such as brightness, hoarseness, etc. by means of modeling their contours during singing performance.

1.2 Instrumental gestures for computer music performance

Advances in computer music technologies have permitted the appearance of many different synthesis trends applied to the construction of musical instrument synthesizers, opening new ways of music creation. On one hand, these new technologies are being applied to construct very realistic computer synthesis models for traditional instruments with many different applications, for instance to composers, who are able to listen to a 'synthesized' performance of their compositions at home, in front of their desktop computer. On the other hand, such advances are bringing many possibilities for the creation of new instruments, and the proliferation of new ways of interaction with musical sound synthesis.

Nowadays, a great variety of electronic music is being created by means of the new possibilities of digital music instruments, resulting into great success in many contexts. However, electronic music cannot be compared to traditional acoustic music performance in terms of expressivity. This is a spread complain that has caused the computer music community to put effort in capturing the expressive characteristics of music performance. Since the audio perceptual features of music performance are the result of the combination of a music instrument and a performer, new synthesis technologies need to model both the musical instrument itself and the performance action (gestures) applied to it. Indeed, in spite of the various methods available to synthesize sound, the ultimate musical

expression of those sounds still falls upon the capture of gestures used for control and performance [RWDD97].

In music performance, performers apply physical actions to musical instruments in order to produce sound. Depending on the characteristics of the interaction, these physical actions may become very complex. The complexity of the interaction is due mainly to the manner in which the music instrument produces sound. A very basic classification of the interaction with the instrument in terms of 'sound-producing' gestures¹ makes a major distinction into two classes of instruments: *excitation-instantaneous* musical instruments and *excitation-continuous* musical instruments. In the case of excitation-instantaneous musical instruments, the musician carry out the interaction exciting the instrument mainly by means of instantaneous actions in the shape of impulsive hits or plucks, producing different sounds by the changing characteristics of the impulsive actions and the conditions in which they are produced. This makes normally easier to model the physical actions involved in sound production. Examples of this kind of instruments are drums, piano, guitar, etc. Conversely, in excitation-continuous musical instruments, the performer produces sound by exciting the instrument continuously during performance, and achieves variations of sound by continuous modulations of the physical actions involved. This fact makes more difficult to model the dynamic characteristics of the gestures. Examples of this class of instruments are woodwind and brass instruments, bowed strings, and the singing voice, among others. In this sense, there is more room for improvement in the automatic rendering of input control contours for excitation-continuous musical instruments, which result more difficult to imitate.

The result of the physical actions in music performance is the modification of the perceptual characteristics of the produced sound. Thus, gestures involved in the sound production process in music performance (we will refer to them as 'instrumental gestures') have been mainly studied in two different domains: the *physical action domain* and the *perceptual audio feature domain*. Each domain presents its own advantages and disadvantages. Although the information extracted from the physical actions of the performer represents with completeness the sound production mechanisms, it is often far from being directly related to the perceptual feature modifications that is causing. This is strongly linked with

¹we will see a classification of gestures in the subsequent sections

some characteristics of the current synthesis methods used in computer music.

A basic classification of musical instrument synthesis methods makes a major distinction into *signal models* and *physical models*. This classification is based on the approach taken when 'imitating' the musical instrument. Physical models are based on analytical formulae describing the acoustic and mechanical behaviour of the musical instrument and its structure, i.e., the sound production mechanisms. They allow input control by means of a reasonable low number of parameters that are directly related to the physical actions applied by performers. In contrast, signal models are based on the perceptual attributes of sound. They are built on top of abstract mathematical structures that store spectral or temporal properties of sound. The input controls for this kind of synthesizers, far away from the production mechanisms of sound, are much closer to the perception of sound, leading to a major flexibility and simplicity of analysis.

Several options are open to be taken into account the gestures when designing strategies for controlling musical instrument synthesizers. On one hand, gestures can be extracted from the physical action domain and applied as inputs to physical model synthesizers in order to control them as a human would do. For realistic sound synthesis, this assume high fidelity of sound synthesis, which is fairly achieved in most physical model based musical instrument synthesizers. On the other hand, assuming that every perceptual feature can be extracted from analyzing audio performance recordings, gestures can be extracted by considering the contours of such perceptual features. This would allow applying them as inputs to a signal model synthesizer, which a higher sound fidelity in most of cases. Other interesting approaches may benefit from this dual view, like 'hybrid' synthesizers in which both the physical action and perceptual feature contours are taken into account.

When dealing with real time synthesis, more important is the manner in which the mapping of physical domain gestural data onto synthesis parameters is done. Most of the work in this area has traditionally focused on one-to-one mapping of control values to synthesis parameters. In the case of physical modeling synthesis, this approach may make sense due to the fact that the relation between gesture input and sound production is already part of the synthesis model. However, with signal models, this one-to-one mapping may not be the most appropriate, since it does not take advantage of the opportunity signal models allow for higher

level couplings between control gestures.

1.3 A need for synthesis

Modern synthesizers have reached nowadays very high sound fidelity and quality, offering a wide range of synthesis parameters that are not always clearly related to the way in which the instrument is played. These parameters, while not always being capable of representing the performance possibilities of the instrument, must be tuned manually in order to get the performance naturalness and/or expressivity that a human performer would introduce. This means that the user must spend time in learning how to tune those parameters when trying to avoid the performance know-how for a particular instrument.

Particularly in signal model-based synthesis, which has provided more fidelity in reproducing the sound of real instruments, the sonic space of a particular instrument is reduced to collecting singular samples that represent static points of the space, leading to representation that does not correspond to the dynamic characteristics of music performance. Therefore, the process of synthesis is limited to the retrieval of best-matching discrete samples, local transformations and "jumps" from one point (or its surroundings) to another, thus restricting (in the best case) the context awareness to how to transform those static points and connect them. These limitations get more important when synthesizing excitation-continuous musical instruments, due to the richness of the sound nuances taking place during performance. In this sense, a better understanding of the instrumental gestures used in each situation of a performance is needed if excitation-continuous musical instrument synthesis is to be improved.

Hence, there is a clear need to quantitatively represent instrumental gestures in one or both domains, and study how a particular instrument is controlled in every context. By means of such a detailed description and analysis, computer models of musical instruments would take into account the performance habits of each instrument, and rely on a 'code' of its input controls accordingly. Therefore, the available control means for driving a particular synthesizer will not just stay at the level of a sequence of notes², but go beyond and represent

²the traditional way by which musical scores are represented

how the musician transform the musical message into a sequence of instrumental gestures, rendering them by means of a established intermediate step (see Figure 1.1). The existence of such a particular knowledge for each instrument would definitely help to synthesize more realistic sounds with the already existent synthesis conceptions, or even improve the classical approaches for synthesis.

Figure 1.1: Schematic representation of the sound synthesis process making use of a gesture renderer component. Two components are represented, corresponding to rendering gestures in the physical action domain, and rendering gestures in the perceptual sound feature domain. The renderer components make use of gesture models stored in a database and a possible matching of gestures both domains. The inputs to the sound synthesis components are the result of the concatenation of the rendered gestures.

1.4 Objectives and focus of this work

The main objective of this work is propose some techniques to approach the problem of quantitatively characterizing instrumental gestures in excitation continuous musical instruments. For doing so, we must survey the approaches that have been already taken for solving this analysis problem both from the audio

perceptual feature domain and from the physical action domain and present the way to a definition of a general procedure for classification and description of the instrumental gesture as a music performance unit that musicians use during the interpretation of a score.

We will consider instrumental gestures as time-series continuous contours of features or descriptors relevant for producing sound, extracted either from the perceptual audio feature domain or from the action gestures applied to the instrument. These contours must get contextualized and appropriately segmented by means of a manual or automatic alignment to the performed score by a top-down approach (see Figure 1.2). In this sense, a prior identification of gesture typologies, depending on their context, functionality, instrument, and analysis domain, is needed. Although not understood by some as a musical instrument, a considerable number of excitation-continuous musical instruments have been designed following the voice paradigm. We will pay special attention to singing voice because of its particular issues and the number and complexity of gestures used.

By considering gestures as a space-time trajectories, we aim at proposing a framework that allows us to recognize and segment such gestures by their structural properties, so a meaningful parameterization must be carried out. The framework must allow to quantitatively 'code' the possible execution deviations for a given structure pattern, and eventually study the correlation or mapping between features from both domains. The completeness of the description must provide the means for reconstructing trajectories for being applied to synthesis, so that it is possible to set and give real use to a recently so called *Gesture Description Interchange Format* (GDIF) [JKG06].

1.5 Structure of the proposal

After this short introduction to the topic of instrumental gestures in excitation-continuous musical instruments, we give in Chapter 2 a short background on instrumental gestures, and some relevant research addressing how they have been studied from different perspectives, even if not related directly with music, as it is the case of prosody analysis in speech. Then, in a second part of the chapter, we overview some of the control trends in some of the state-of-the-art synthesis

Figure 1.2: General overview of the top-down approach for the capture of instrumental gestures, both by extracting physical action feature contours and by extracting sound perceptual features. The mapping between the two domains, when physical models of instruments are not considered, becomes easier as one goes down to a 'symbolic' level where gestures are matched one to one. Of course, it is not only the score matching component which gives context to the contours in each domain, but also the extracted contours and constraints set by the complementary domain.

techniques. Chapter 2 presents some initial contributions to the topic, both for the automatic description of instrumental gestures, and for the application of such description for expressive performance analysis and synthesis. Finally, in Chapter 4, we conclude by introducing some proposed approaches for building up a framework for the automatic quantitative description and extraction of instrumental gestures.

Chapter 2

Background and Relevant Research

In this Section, we shortly present the basic elements of music performance, focusing mainly on the performer and the instrument, followed by a definition of instrumental gestures, understood as the sound-producing gestures in music performance. Then, we survey some of the strategies taken to face the problem of the extraction and parameterization of instrumental gestures (both from the audio analysis domain and from the physical action domain), even in the case that they are not treated as such. Then, we outline a short review of control possibilities of the commonly used synthesis techniques and put them in contrast to the parameterization that is performed by some of the approaches presented.

2.1 Elements of music performance

The sound we perceive from a musical performance can be roughly decomposed into a chain consisting on the following three elements: the composition, the performer, and the instrument. As the composition, we understand the basic musical creation or makeup of the musical piece, conveying the contents of a musical idea represented by a time-structured sequence of note events in a well-defined score. For the instrument, we understand the physical object that allows producing the musical piece described in the composition by a variety of physical actions applied to it. Finally, we understand the performer as the human being

that transforms the note events presents in the composition (score) into musical sounds by applying the physical actions allowed by each particular instrument. This is illustrated in Figure 2.1.

Figure 2.1: Simple decomposition of the process of music performance.

Even when the composition score is notated precisely, there are still many decisions that a performer makes, depending on her/his wishes for expressing a particular emotion, or either on musical style or instrument practical constrains. The process of a performer deciding how to perform music that has been previously composed and notated is termed as interpretation or performance. We will make use of the second term in this dissertation. None of these three elements are not independent from each other. Yet the score, that may have sense as an isolated element, is still dependant on the musical instrument and performance style it is intended for. Performer and instrument are not easily treated as different when considering the importance of the interaction taking part during performance. Indeed, successful computer models of musical instrument are already intrinsically containing the performer, since their normal way of being controlled is by means of a sequence of notes and not, in most of cases, strictly the actions applied to them. In this sense, it is difficult to set a physical or logical limit between these two elements (see Figure 2.2) if there is not an intermediate step in which those actions are reflected.

Trained then musicians are able to read a composition or musical piece that they are given in the shape of a score. This musical document that may get very different meanings depending on how it is performed. Music performance as the act of interpreting, structuring and physically realizing a composition is a complex human activity with many facets: physical, acoustic, physiological, psychological, social, artistic, etc. [Gab99]. We do not want to enter into the discussion of each one of these factors, but even though there is an important part of expression already conveyed in the musical piece to be performed, compositions

Figure 2.2: Where is the logical/physical limit between performer and instrument in computer models for automatic music performance?

might be understood by a musician as a set of instructions they perform by means of a particular instrument and its praxis habits, their musical training, and other aspects to which they have been exposed. In order to be able to properly represent the process of music performance in computer models, it is necessary then to establish a clear differentiation of performer/musician and instrument in which the transformation of the input score into a set of instrumental gestures is considered a process itself. This need is represented in Figure 2.3.

Figure 2.3: Elements of the music performance chain where performer and instrument are distinguished among different domains.

2.2 Instrumental gestures

Biologists define *gesture*, broadly stating, "the notion of gesture is to embrace all kinds of instances where an individual engages in movements whose communicative intent is paramount, manifest, and openly acknowledged" [NPL86]. In its simplest sense, the term *gesture* has been mainly treated as to the way human beings move their body to communicate, although gestures are used for everything from pointing at a person to get their attention to conveying information

about space and temporal characteristics [Ken90]. Evidence indicates that, for instance, gesturing does not simply embellish spoken language, but is part of the language generation process [ML82].

Although sometimes hard to differentiate, musicians performing a particular piece make use of two types of gestures, according to an act-symbol dicotomy [NPL86]. This dichotomy refers to the notion that some gestures are pure actions, while others are intended as symbols. For instance, an action gesture occurs when a person chops wood or counts money, while a symbolic gesture occurs when a person makes the "okay" sign or puts their thumb out to hitchhike. Examples of each one of these senses are, for an action gesture, purely playing a pair of notes present in the score; and for a symbol gesture, playing such pair of notes by means of a extreme *staccato* articulation. Naturally, some action gestures can also be interpreted as symbols (semiogenesis), as illustrated in a spy novel, when an agent carrying an object in one hand has important meaning; or in a musical performance, the voluntary omission of some note.

Among the musical gestures, one can find composition gestures and performance gestures. Composition gestures, while not physical, are already at the music creation step, constituting the composition itself. They can be understood as isolated notes, groups of notes, or annotations referring to the manner in which some notes (e.g. *crescendo*, *legato*) are to be played. They conveying a particular musical message and are expressed explicitly in the score. Conversely, performance gestures are not explicit and lay on the physical domain. They are understood as the voluntary (or constrained) gestures produced by the performer during the transformation of the score into musical sound. Within performance gestures, Wanderley [WD04] proposes a classification of performance gestures into *ancillary gestures* and *instrumental gestures*. He refers to instrumental gestures as the ones involved in the sound production process (e.g. moving the bow in violin performance), while ancillary gestures are considered to be produced by the performer as additional body movements, not involved directly in the sound production mechanisms, but linked to the performance and being able to communicate some emotional content, and even to modify slightly the sound properties (e.g. body movements of pianists).

Cadoz [Cad88] proposes a definition of instrumental gestures as follows:

”Instrumental gesture will be considered as a communication modality specific to the gestural channel, complementary to free gestures, and characterized by the following: it is applied to a material object and there is physical interaction with the object; within this interaction, specific physical phenomena are produced whose forms and dynamical evolution can be controlled by the one applying the gesture; these phenomena can convey communicational messages (information)”.

He considers this transfer of information as a specificity of instrumental gestures, when compared to other ergodic or ancillary gestures. He reminds that ”not all gestures have the same function on an instrumental object”. Therefore, he proposes an instrumental gesture typology (see Figure 2.4) according to their function:

- **Exciter gestures** - the ones that convey the energy that will be found in the sonic result (e.g. blowing in wind instruments).
- **Modulation gestures** - the ones that modify the properties of the instrument but in which energy does not participate directly in the sonic result. These can be divided in two groups:
 - **Parametric modulation gestures** - the ones that change continually a parameter (e.g. variation of bow pressure in violin performance)
 - **Structural modulation gestures** - the ones that modify the structure of the object (e.g. opening or closing a hole in a flute).
- **Selection gestures** - the ones that perform a choice among different but equivalent structures to be used during a performance (e.g. the direction of bowing in violin performance). There is neither energy transfer (in the sense of exciter gestures) nor an object modification (as in the case of structural modulation gestures).

It is remarkable that usually none of these gestures come alone during performance, and it is difficult sometimes to distinguish a single functionality of a gesture. An example of gesture combining exciter functionality and modulation

Figure 2.4: Classification of musical gestures, and classification of instrumental gestures according to their function as proposed by Cadoz [Cad88]

functionality is for instance a vibrato in singing voice performance (parametric modulation). Other example of mixed functionality is violin bowing can be seen as well as exciter plus selection plus modulation gesture, because the performer bows in order to excite the body, but chooses where to bow (bow-bridge distance).

The generality of this classification does not prevent instrumental gestures from being affected by several factors. Some annotations present in the score help the performer to execute the musical piece and guides her/him in choosing some gestures or modulating some parameters, as it is for instance the case of a crescendo annotation, that makes the musician to increase progressively the air-flow in saxophone performance. From the information not present explicitly in the score, instrumental gestures are constrained by several factors from which we classify them into three: *physical limitations*, *instrument or performance habits* and *performer wishes*. Some physical limitations force some gestures to be executed at some moments, like for instance changing the direction of the bow as it arrives to the maximum displacement (there is still some room for deciding whether the change), or the pronunciation of some consonants in singing

voice performance, which force a structural change that modifies or truncates perceptual parameters as for instance fundamental frequency. Other important factors is more related to the instrument being played or the performance habits acquired. This refers for instance to the fingering, which will presumably be different in each string instrument. The third main group of factors or constrains includes all variations and deviations that the performer introduces due to her/his own wishes (more related to expression), like for instance vibrato or tremolo, legato articulation, etc. not present in the score. It is clear that the procedure in which instrumental gestures are to be captured and quantitatively characterized must definitely take into account these three factors and how some of them may interact at the same time. Of course, the set of gestures, its classification, and the constrains affecting them, will be different for every instrument and/or instrument family.

2.3 About instrumental gesture description

2.3.1 Introduction

Treated sometimes as a multi-level audio description, with a straightforward relationship with the composition score, and sometimes as body movements, either with the intention of producing the sound corresponding to the musical message conveyed in the score, or just as a expression part of the performer, this section gives introduces the overview that will be carried out in next sections about the approaches that have been taken in order to capture instrumental gestures, both from the the analysis of performance audio recordings. First, the two main domains from which instrumental gestures are studied are defined. Then, it is introduced the relationship between expressive performance analysis and instrumental gestures. Then, some particularities of the singing voice as a musical instrument are also outlined.

2.3.2 Audio analysis versus physical measurements

As stated already in previous chapter, there exist mainly two domains from where one is able to grasp information about how a particular musician trans-

lates the score into sound, i.e., information about performance (instrumental) gestures that are used. These two domains are the 'sound domain' and the 'physical actions' domain, being the latter less studied. The simplicity and low-cost of the audio measurement device (say microphones) makes the audio analysis more popular and 'easy-access' [WD04]. Conversely, the measurement difficulties movement tracking systems based on sensors and/or computer vision have left the physical action domain being less studied. Another possible cause comes from the fact that physical model based synthesizers don't provide normally the sound fidelity offered by sample-based synthesizers, and it is more difficult to render their input parameters than some simple perceptual parameters (e.g. pitch, amplitude) needed to control a sample-based synthesizer. This is indeed a drawback of sample-based synthesizers compared to physical models when the aim is to render natural sounding performances: only a few samples are stored in the database, in which the performer is already included and constrained by that set of samples.

Many attempts have been made to extract information about musical performance characteristics from both domains. In the sound domain, these instrumental gestures are treated sometimes as 'expressive resources' [Sch95], [dPCD⁺04], [Can97] or 'articulations' in a general way. Physical action measurements have been carried out by different perspectives and with different aims. For instance, Wanderley [WVN⁺05] analyzed quantitatively, by means of computer vision techniques, what he calls *ancillary gestures*, i.e., non obvious gestures of musicians during clarinet performance that are not directly related to sound production; and Rasamimanana [Ras05] studied the characteristics and classified bow strokes in terms of bow acceleration and speed measurements. In the subsequent sections, we will go through some different approaches for both domains: the *audio* analysis and *physical action* analysis.

2.3.3 Relation to expressive performance analysis

In human musical performance, acoustic or perceptual changes in sound are organized in a complex way by the performer in order to communicate different emotions or expressions to the listener. Musicians do not play exactly what is written in the score. This fact makes expressive music performance become

an interesting topic of study from the perspective of gestures. In its simplest sense, the term 'expressive performance' is applied to those elements of a musical communication that depend on musician's personal response and that vary between different interpretations or styles. Performers enrich the sound using some resources as for instance timing deviations (e.g. *accelerando*, *ritardando*), dynamics (e.g. *crescendo*, *decrescendo*), modulations (e.g. *vibrato*, *tremolo*) and articulations (e.g. *legato*, *staccato*). When studying music expressivity, it becomes necessary to measure and represent those resources in order to characterize the performance, i.e., how a certain piece has been played by a particular performer and how these resources result in acoustic or perceptual changes. By acoustic or perceptual changes, authors in [dPCD⁺04] understand those changes as deviations from what is understood as the 'basic elements' that are supposed to be used in the interpretation of the musical sound following what they call a *neutral performance*. Indeed, even a neutral performance is already carrying some gestural information due to the possible 'playing' constraints presented in Chapter 1.

In our case, we understand expressive performance as the choice of the performer to use particular performance (instrumental) gestures, adapting them to the context, and giving them the desired shape. This shape, along with the context¹ in which it is performed, apart from explaining the type of gesture used, gives also important information about the style or expression being conveyed. We mean that although they may belong to a certain typology or pattern (e.g. the action of changing the direction of the bow in violin performance), the manners that the performer is choosing to execute those gestures, contain expressive information. This is, for the case of the action of changing the direction of the bow in violin performance could be executed in many different manners, not only related to general constraints like for instance tempo. In this sense, understanding and modeling performance instrumental gestures leads to understand and model expressive performance. Therefore, the relevant expressive performance analysis approaches that have been taken so far, both audio analysis-based and physical gesture measurement-based, are worth to be read. Some of these approaches will be referenced in the following subsections trying to give a 'gestural' perspective. A nice review of the state-of-the-art computational models of expressive

¹the context may be determined for instance by the use of some score-performance matching techniques, see Section 2.4.3

performance, and some relevant references can be found in [WG04].

Many efforts have been already put into the analysis of expressive performance by means of studying the audio from real performance recordings. Research has been focused mainly on tempo and dynamics modulations during performance [Dix00]. These modulations, however, in most of cases are extracted as the sampling of timing deviations and dynamics at each note in the performance. Some studies already deal with inter-note descriptions from audio, such as the level of 'legato' between two notes [DPCD⁺01] or the attack descriptors [Sch97]. Some other tried to extract expressive performance information from an analysis of directly measured sound-producing physical actions involved during music performance [Ras05] [WVN⁺05]. In this sense, next sections provide an overview of some techniques that, although having been applied to explicitly extract expressive information from human performance, are dealing with what we call here *instrumental gestures*.

2.3.4 Singing voice

Singing voice is known to be the most complex musical instrument in terms of timbre variability and articulation control, so natural singing voice becomes one of the most challenging aspects of musical instrument synthesis. Recent research on sample-based singing voice synthesis has reached high quality voice models [Bon01], but the inclusion of a model for the articulation gestures, understood for instance as transitions from note to note, remains still an open problem. Normally, the majority of instrumental gestures in singing voice synthesis are sampled and stored in the database as part of the samples, although some other like (e.g. vibrato) are generated by super-imposing them to the melody contour. This limitation restricts the naturalness and flexibility of synthesis by reducing the freedom to transform them for a specific context, due mainly to the lack of a quantitative description. Even in the case of a physical model-based synthesizer [Coo91], where its input controls are more related to the voice production and articulation, it is very hard to In this sense, we pay special attention to the singing voice because of its complexity in terms of gestures for natural sounding synthesis. The gross contour of the voice pitch, which we may view as a sort of macro-intonation, is decided by the composer. The singer adds emotion in the domain of

the micro-intonation. However, some micro-intonation nuances are not caused by the performer in order to give any expression or style, but by the voice production [Sun87] [Los03]. Thus, singing voice presents some special characteristics, due mainly to phonation, that might be considered in a special way. While still a excitation-continuous instrument, the production of some consonants constrains the contours of amplitude and fundamental frequency independently from the intentions of the singer. That is what some people from the speech community call the 'micro-prosody'. An example of this is illustrated in Figure 2.5. This modulations or discontinuities of pitch and amplitude contours could be seen as 'ancillary' gestures and not part of the instrumental gestures. This nuances or modulations can be seen as well as a sort of gestures put by the performer for articulating words in a desired way, thus dividing them into word-articulatory and as musically constrained by the score. The pronunciation of some consonants in certain contexts may influence on those gestures intentionally performed by the singer. Yet the manner in which one could separate these two classes of nuances is an interesting issue in this case, and some propositions will be stated in Chapter 4.

Much research has been active in the speech processing area during the last years in order to model the prosody characteristics of the spoken language ([FO96] [SKFL⁺01] [EC02]), while the singing voice remained more unattended. Only a few researches have tried to construct computational models for singing voice gestures apart from the phonetic articulations. For instance, in [Ort01], a general model for the note-to-note transitions by applying some rules [Sun89] already extracted by a analysis-by-synthesis approach [Ber96] is adopted. However, this model results too general and not flexible enough for representing strong differences between performers or styles. An interesting work is presented in [SUA02], where the authors tried to evaluate the perception of pitch dynamic characteristics of singing voice by applying some 'ad-hoc' models of typical fundamental frequency fluctuations (e.g. overshoot, vibrato, etc.). They model those fluctuations as special cases of second order system responses, dividing them into several classes, depending on their context. Not used for recognition purposes, the models are applied for adding of these gestures. A recent work presented in [MBM06] modeled fundamental frequency and amplitude modulations during note-to-note transitions, following the work carried out in [EC02] for speech.

Figure 2.5: Waveform (top) and pitch contour (bottom) of a short excerpt from a singing voice performance recording. A discontinuity of the pitch contour due to the pronunciation of a unvoiced consonant is indicated by a red box. Intra-note and inter-note segments are segmented and indicated in green. Note boundaries are also segmented.

While obtaining interesting results in classifying between three types of transitions, the amount of data results too small and the models are not able to be applied for synthesis in a general way. For the case of obtaining data from the physical action domain, which is considerably more difficult, author in [Coo91] presented a methodology for extracting control parameters in an physical articulatory vocal tract model, which resulted far from realistic in terms of sound fidelity due to the simplification introduced in the physical model.

2.4 Audio analysis approach

2.4.1 Introduction

As we already introduced in Chapter 1, perceptual sound features able to provide information about the performance must be extracted from audio analysis. We presented previously two main approaches to face the understanding and modeling of the instrumental gestures: description and modeling of gestures by finding the correspondences between audio perceptual features and physical movements (movements involved in the production of sound²), and description and modeling of gestures just by paying attention at the 'sound' domain. For both approaches, common techniques dealing with audio analysis are adopted. No matter whether the information will be later used to recognize some intentions or performance styles (more related to expressivity analysis) or just for modeling the common performance habits of a particular instruments. We have to say that for the latter, not much attention has been put into modeling how instruments are played, with exception of some articulatory models for early synthesizers based on physical models. This is due to the fact that sample-based synthesizers already include the performer's actions in each sample (see Section 2.7).

For both options, it is important the extraction of descriptors perceptually meaningful from audio. As cited in [Jen99b], we can see timbre as that quality which distinguishes two sounds with the same pitch, loudness and duration. Roughly, timbre distinguishes sources of sound (instruments), but performers vary mainly these three attributes in order to convey the musical message contained in the score. Most of authors extracting performance information from audio have focused their attention on these three main sound attributes and tried to find the explanation of other timbric perceptual descriptors as correlations to them (e.g. brightness explained by loudness [Pee04]). This leads to assume loudness and pitch³ as the most important audio low-level descriptors⁴ to deal with and more widely studied in music performance. Loudness (or *intensity*) is normally extracted from the signal as the computation of a short-time signal

²other studies dealt with other perceptual attributes of music performance not directly related to the sound production [WVN⁺05]

³duration is already included in the evolution of these two parameters along time

⁴some authors would treat them as high level descriptors, since their extraction from the audio signal needs of some pre-processing

energy, thus sampling the loudness along time. Pitch is estimated again from a frame-wise analysis of the signal (see Section 2.4.3), so that it is also sampled along time. The sequences of values of loudness and pitch do not have much sense as raw contours, so they need to be put in context, at different levels, and be linked linked to the input score.

2.4.2 Audio description as a multi-level issue

Audio descriptors are defined at different levels. Levels are defined at different temporal contexts. At the lower levels we find the audio signal itself, which is sampled directly from the performance recording. The information at higher levels e.g. note, phrase) is computed from the low-level descriptors (e.g. loudness, pitch) by means of a segmentation of the performance and alignment to the original score. High level descriptors may already provide information from more than one note, while other higher-level descriptors may carry information about more specific information, for instance about a particular note-subsegment. This multi-level scheme is roughly depicted in Figure 2.6. The note-level segmentation serves as a the basic reference or guideline for subsequent groupings or segmentations into the different gestures (from different levels like a 'crescendo' for a group of notes, staccato or legato as a type of articulation, type of attack for one note, etc.) that were used to perform that sequence of notes. When referring to the term 'gesture' in conducting movements or dance movements (might be referred as trajectories) this multi-layered perspective is also considered in other works, for instance is presented in [BF04] and [APMG01], where the reader can find a multi-level, hierarchical decomposition of the movement parameters.

People has paid much attention to the note-level because of the music classical notation (it is the visible object for performers). The note descriptors are normally computed as averaged along the note segment extracted from the prior segmentation, although its calculation might have been carried out during the segmentation process[RK05]. Starting from the extracted descriptions for each note, studies have raised to higher levels (e.g. phrase) in order to, being helped with some structural analysis of the song, obtain high-level performance descriptors. Conversely, it is more difficult to find studies dealing with intra-note or inter-note descriptions, i.e., which use the note-level segmentation for obtaining

Figure 2.6: Schematic representation of multi-level audio description. Note-level segmentation serves as a the basic reference or guideline for subsequent groupings or segmentations into the different gestures.

information about more specific gestural context. In the following subsections, after citing common techniques for segmenting and aligning the performance to the score, we will explore the approaches adopted at different levels of description, say note-level description, intra-note description, inter-note level description, and phrase description.

2.4.3 Score following and automatic transcription

Going back to the decomposition of performance that we presented in Chapter 1, we considered three main elements: score, performer and instrument. Although an important part of the music performance chain [Hon06], we are not considering the listener as a primary part. Since we put as a basis of this work the fact that

the performer will make use of a group of gestures when interpreting the reference score, in order to capture them is important to match the time axis of both domains (*gesture domain* and the *score domain*). Thus, it is important to look at the literature dealing with score following and automatic music transcription, which is considerably extense.

Score following

Authors in [OLS03] define score following as the synchronization of a computer with a performer playing a known musical score. It can be found in the literature that the ultimate goal of score following has been to simulate the behaviour of a musician playing with another, a "synthetic performer", to create a virtual accompanist that will follow the score of the human musician. Typically, a score follower is constituted three main parts [Dan84]: a "listening" part, which analyzes the input audio and extract a set of features important for their relationship to the score (e.g. note being played); a "matching" part, in charge of aligning the incoming audio features or cues to the reference score; and a "accompaniment" part that decides the actions to be performed as to accompany the performer. Each score following system defines a different set of relevant audio features that are sampled in time, and are used as descriptors of the musician's performance (e.g. amplitude, fundamental frequency, etc.). This is depicted in Figure 2.7, where the listening part and matching part have been highlighted due to their relationship to the analysis of performance gestures we are facing in this section.

Figure 2.7: Typical architecture of a score follower.

We understand that an audio feature extraction part, along with a score matching part, are key components of the pre-processing system needed to

analyse instrumental gestures from audio. While the audio feature extraction component tends to be of a common conception among the different systems proposed in the literature dealing with score alignment (see [GKM03] for audio features used in melodic description, and [FP01] in drum track description), different authors addressed and implemented systems, both academic and for commercial applications, in order to face the alignment problem, useful for a high level description of the performance.

In general, automatic alignment of sequences has been a popular research topic in many fields, such as string analysis, molecular biology, and notably speech recognition. The literature is considerably vast, and we only mention a comprehensive overview on the approach in speech recognition [RH93].

Concerning automatic music alignment specifically, the main works are score following techniques tuned for off line use, mostly based on stochastic models ([Dan84],[Rap01],[LCB99], [CLB99]) considering mainly monophonic recordings and making use of dynamic programming techniques. For music containing a drum or percussion part, aligning the notes is more difficult for the proposed methods. Beat alignment algorithms specialize on aligning the drum hits in a performance with a percussion score representation, trying to ignore the interleaved melodic notes. The reader can find an interesting review of the state-of-the-art score following techniques in [OLS03].

Automatic transcription

Transcription of music is defined to be the act of listening to a piece of music and of writing down the musical notation for the sounds that constitute the piece. In other terms, this means transforming an acoustic signal into a symbolic representation, which comprises musical events and their parameters [KVES01]. The main difference between a automatic music transcription systems and score followers is the existence of a reference score, although an important part of the ideas implemented in a score following system can be shared with a music transcription system or any other system intended to automatically extract the location of musical events. Many studies address the problem of music transcription as the extraction of sound features or descriptors related to the occurring positions and pitches of note events in musical recordings, either monophonic (saxophone

as a excitation-continuous instrument [GGAA03]; singing voice as a excitation-continuous instrument [AK04], [VKE03]; piano as a excitation-instantaneous instrument [Rap02]) or polyphonic ([Mar96], [RK05]), and a posterior decision stage that may utilize some tempo or beat information extracted from the onset sequence. A classical view of the architecture of a music transcription system is depicted in figure 2.8, where the two main components related to pitched note events (onset detection and fundamental frequency estimation) are depicted.

Figure 2.8: Classical structure of a music transcription system.

Onset detection has been widely studied from different perspectives. The classical approach (e.g. [Dix01]) has been to create a power evolution function from the sound signal (usually via smoothing) and find onsets often by searching for peaks in the difference function. Derivations from this idea brought the development a method for refining the location of an onset by examining the relative energy difference function in various frequency bands [Kla99]. Also other recent approaches make use of diverse machine learning techniques for this purpose [AP03], [DG02]. A very detailed review on onset detection algorithms is found in [BDA⁺04]. While still an unsolved problem, specially for polyphonic sound, fundamental frequency estimation has been approached mainly from the music and speech fields. A first classification for the perspectives in which it has been approached would divide them into temporal signal analysis and spectral analysis. Temporal analysis-based approaches focus mainly on the auto-correlation function (ACF) [dCK02], while spectral analysis based approaches deal with harmonic matching approaches [MB94] and and spectral periodicity. Other methods are based on modeling the auditory system [TK00]. A historical review on fundamental frequency estimation can be found in [Ger03].

More recent probabilistic studies on music transcription ([RK05], [Rap99]) already include the musical note (often with some musicological knowledge) as an entity, but even if one looks at the simplest case of monophonic music, not much research is found dealing with transcription beyond the note level. Even some probabilistic models that incorporate the idea of intra-note segments in their acoustic models come out with just a note-level transcription. However, this segmentation into notes already sets a synchronization for gesture recognition, although gestures are not yet considered as such.

2.4.4 Note level descriptions

Among the possible descriptors providing useful information in terms of instrumental gestures, most of the information is carried by amplitude and fundamental frequency evolution over time. Due to the straightforward relationship between the score and the performance, most of the studies have put their temporal axis on top of the score or MIDI representation, sampling the value of amplitude and fundamental frequency at each note of the performance. Some other descriptors extracted also as a global value for each note, as for instance brightness descriptors, give more particular information on how each note has been performed.

Traditionally, note-level descriptions include onset time (also onset deviation from its corresponding score note), duration (also duration deviation), global note amplitude or loudness, and fundamental frequency in terms of normalized MIDI note. These descriptors give a note-level description of the performance, considered as a sequence of events, and are extracted by means of a previous automatic segmentation or sometimes by human-assisted segmentation.

Representing the knowledge on the musical performance as a sequence of events, this level corresponds to the same level of abstraction of the MIDI⁵ representation of the performance, e.g., as obtained from a sequencer (MIDI list events). This abstraction has been used in [dPCD⁺04] in order to obtain a similar event description from an audio performance, considered a sequence of notes. In Figure 2.9, the n -th note of the sequence is described by the pitch value $FR(n)$, the Onset time $O(n)$, and Duration $DR(n)$ (which are time-related parameters), and by a set of timbre-related parameters: Intensity or Loudness $I(n)$, Brightness

⁵<http://www.midi.org>

$BR(n)$ (measured as the centroid of the spectral envelope [GG78]), and energy envelope, described by Attack Duration $AD(n)$ and Envelope Centroid $EC(n)$ (i.e., the temporal centroid of the dynamic profile of the note [Pee04]). They obtained this representation from a short-time spectral analysis by a semiautomatic segmentation. Within this set of descriptors that they consider to belong to note-level, it is possible to find two of them already referring to a deeper level. These descriptors are the Attack Duration $AD(n)$, understood as the main temporal increase of the note (or directly the duration of the attack segment), and the envelope centroid $EC(n)$. To our understanding, these descriptors are more related to the intra-note level description (see Section 2.4.7), because they give information about the quality of the temporal evolution of the amplitude inside the note.

Figure 2.9: Schematic representation of the descriptors attached to a note [dPCD⁺04].

2.4.5 Phrase level descriptions

We consider here as a phrase a set of two or more adjacent notes in a performance. Phrasing has been received traditionally much more attention than for instance intra-note characteristics of music performance. Many studies in music performance have dealt with diverse aspects of phrasing. The main two dimensions taken into account have been dynamics and tempo. In expressive

music performance, tempo and dynamics modulations are considered the most prominent ways to affect the expression at phrase level [WG04] [Dix00]. The melody contour is already defined by the composition score, so at phrase level, it is more important to study the evolution of intensity or loudness of the sequence of notes and their onset deviations from the score. Tempo contours are obtained by extracting onset times of notes and relating them to the onset times of their counterpart in the score, while dynamics contours are extracted by sampling the loudness or amplitude of each of the performed notes, by means of an automatic or manual segmentation.

Although tempo and dynamics are sometimes expressed explicitly in the composition score, studies in music performance have dealt with describing how performers deviate from the score by means of quantitative or qualitatively descriptions of such contours. Authors in [WT03] has worked with manual annotations of different pieces, having a general dynamics curve: intra-note segments are not considered (annotations have been carried out manually). Moreover, dynamics are considered to affect a whole or several beats. From a dynamics curve obtained by sampling values at each note or beat, it is extracted a curve defined at different hierarchical levels. Curves are modeled as second order polynomials. At the top level, including the whole measure, the coefficients of polynomial curve are fitted to the loudness sampled values. Then, in the following level, the measure is subdivided, and the residual loudness values of each new phrase (obtained by subtracting them from the estimated curve in the level above) are used again to fit a new polynomial, and so on (see Figure 2.10) until reaching a detailed enough level of abstraction.

A similar approach dealing with hierarchical segmentation of a performance is taken in [CdPdSV98]. Authors consider four levels of hierarchy, consisting in *note*, *word*, *semiphase*, and *phrase*. This is depicted in Figure 2.11. Although not used as a quantitative characterization of a real recording, they modify the expressive content of a given neutral performance by applying amplitude curve profiles (defined *a priori*) to each one of these four levels. The curves to be applied to a certain quantity are described by five values (see Figure 2.12): t , pos , g_1 , g_2 , g_3 where t is the type of curve (e.g. -1 cusp, 0 triangle, 1 parabola); p is the position of the curve vertex; g_0 , g_1 , g_2 indicate the variations in a perceptual scale at the beginning, at the curve vertex and at the end of the curve. The curve

Figure 2.10: Dynamics curves, estimated as quadratic polynomials at different successive phrase abstraction levels [WT03].

starts at the beginning of the first note of the group and it ends at the note off of the last note of the group.

Figure 2.11: Bar 57, 58, 59, 60 from Mozart clarinet concert in A Major K622 with hierarchical segmentation [CdPdSV98].

Figure 2.12: Typologies of amplitude curves applicable to a group of notes or to a note[CdPdSV98].

Combination of dynamics and tempo contours along time has been approached in [WG04]. They studied different performance styles in playing piano by studying contours of dynamics and tempo, and visualized their evolution as trajectories in 2D space, one dimension for each parameter. They clustered trajectories of a length of 2 beats in order to find an alphabet, as it is depicted in Figure 2.13. Such an approach results very interesting when combining several perceptual parameters extracted from audio. This interesting approach is not yet further developed for synthesis, although its possibilities for studying or modifying the expressive content of expressive performance are clear.

Figure 2.13: A "Mozart performance alphabet" (cluster prototypes) computed by segmentation, mean and variance normalization, and clustering, from performances of Mozart piano sonatas by six pianists. To indicate directionality, dots mark the end points of segments. Shaded regions indicate the variance within a cluster [WG04].

Author in [Bat04] used piecewise cubic Bézier curves to model the evolution of energy, fundamental frequency and spectral centroid in sustained vowel singing voice performances. For each perceptual descriptor, contour curvature is analyzed, and a set of critical points are extracted. Then, the attractors a cubic Bézier curve are fit to each segment defined by two adjacent critical points. No structural analysis is used for the segmentation so it is difficult to somehow 'code' instrumental gestures in a meaningful way.

2.4.6 Inter-note level descriptions

The importance of a articulation in excitation-continuous musical instruments has not received yet a proper response in terms of detailed analysis of how performers connect adjacent notes. By descriptions belonging to the inter-note level, we understand here how to describe the amplitude and fundamental frequency modulations carried during transitions from note to note, although other descriptors can be taken into consideration. Only a few studies have dealt with this level of description. Among the possible causes of this lack of formal studies, the fact that existing sample-based synthesizers base their functioning manner on retrieving the best suited samples from a set of pre-recorded transitions has a prominent

importance. More work has been carried out from an analysis point of view, and dealing with amplitude evolution during transitions. Yet it is a difficult task to define the limits of a transition between two adjacent notes.

Amplitude modulations during transitions are studied in [dPCD⁺04], where we see how from time-related parameters of two successive notes (e.g. duration or onset time), descriptors like Inter Onset Interval $IOI(n) = O(n+1) - O(n)$ and Legato $L(n) = DR(n)/IOI(n)$ parameters are derived. This is illustrated in Figure 2.14, where the amplitude envelope of a violin note is depicted along with some descriptors. These descriptors, while giving information about the articulation, keep hidden the instrumental gesture as a continuous modulation, since they have been inherited from piano performance analysis. It is not possible to reconstruct amplitude or energy contour from them, thus it is not possible to apply them for synthesis. These descriptors are suitable for studies strictly based on analysis, or for modifying the articulation of a recorded performance.

Figure 2.14: Extracted fundamental frequency F_0 of a portion of a singing voice performance. (Top) Melody component related to the estimated F_0 . (Bottom) *Overshoot*, and *Preparation* as modulations occurring during transition [SUA02].

In terms of fundamental frequency, authors in [MBL06] use a probabilistic

approach based on Hidden Markov Models to automatically segment and recognize significant transition types, defined *a priori* by observation, in singing voice performance. They define their transition limits by looking both at the fundamental frequency evolution along time, and the timbric variations. They use these recognition techniques in order to rate the mimicry respect to a reference singer, although they don't base their similarity measures on any quantitative description of fundamental frequency contours. Contrarily, a mathematical formulation for the generation of fundamental frequency contours for several transitions and modulations is found in [SUA02]. They use a constrained second order system response in order to model the evolution of fundamental frequency during transitions. None of these works take into account the possible constraints introduced by the playing habits of the instruments they analyze.

2.4.7 Intra-note level descriptions

In excitation-continuous musical instruments, it has been traditionally considered a note segmentation constituted by four segments, namely *attack*, *decay*, *sustain*, and *release* (decay segment is not always considered), used already in the early synthesizer conceptions [Ber76]. Such a segmentation, is suitable to be applied for performance analysis and characterization purposes, as it is found in several works. The attack part of each note, sometimes only considered when a note is coming from silence, provides perceptually meaningful characteristics of how the initial articulation of such note was performed. In harmonic sounds it is defined as the portion of sound before partial frequencies and amplitude values reach a stable value (maintained during sustain segment). In case the sustain segment is not present, either because the note is a short one, the attack and release parts are considered to be the increase and decrease of energy, maintained during the sustain segment in case it exists) or until: Except for vibrato and tremolo, energy and fundamental frequency are stable during the sustain segment, as it can be observed in Figure 2.15.

Although strongly dependant on the instrument played, these segments are present in both most of excitation-continuous musical instruments, and also in some instantaneous-excitation musical instruments. Author in [Jen99a] studied partial amplitude envelope of isolated notes of different musical instruments.

Figure 2.15: Two notes Excerpt from a singing voice performance of The Beatles' 'Yesterday'. From top to bottom: waveform, partial frequencies, fundamental frequency, and harmonic energy. Increase and decrease of harmonic energy can be seen in the attack and release segments respectively.

He presented an intra-note segmentation algorithm based on the analysis of the envelope curvature for each one of the analyzed partials, in the context of a deep model of the timbre properties of the instruments (see Figure 2.9). Once the limits between intra-note segments are found, each part of the envelope is modeled by an exponential function partial envelope. It is clear that for any accurate model intending to represent amplitude, considering every partial is the most realistic approach, but it results in too much information not representing gesture but timbre. More simplistic is the approach taken in [Sch95], where the attack part is considered as the portion of sound from the note onset to the global

maximum of the energy envelope.

Figure 2.16: Original and recreated amplitude envelope of fundamental partial in four different instruments. Split points between attack, sustain, and release parts are denoted with a '+' sign [Jen99a].

Although not strictly giving a description of the intra-note segments of a performed notes, it is interesting the work by Dannenberg [DPD98] dealing with trumpet envelopes. In the article, they report the extraction of the temporal centroid of trumpet notes and used such features to classify them into different groups. Then, they applied such groupings to the application to an expressive synthesis framework combining instrument and simple performance models [DD98]. In the work presented in [dPCD⁺04], two amplitude envelope descriptors are extracted from violin performance recordings. These descriptors are (see Figure 2.9) the Attack Duration $AD(n)$, understood as the main temporal increase of the note (or directly the duration of the attack segment), and the envelope centroid $EC(n)$. Again, although giving quantities to some of the note amplitude properties, is not enough for reconstructing such contour and control a synthesis engine.

An important gesture used in excitation-continuous musical instruments is vibrato and tremolo. They are typically used during the sustain segment of a note, and consist in a modulation of fundamental frequency and amplitude

modulations respectively. The rate of vibrato, while stay typically around 6 Hz [Sun87], may vary, as well as the modulation depth. Several works reported methodologies to extract and parameterize vibrato [RDS⁺99] [HB98], but only a few dealt studied the extraction and parameterization of vibrato in the context of music performance [DH96].

2.5 Physical action approach

The extraction of an organized set of descriptors from measuring physical movements from physical action approach is what we call the physical action approach, already introduced in previous Sections and referred by Wanderley [WD04] as *direct acquisition* of gestures. In the same way as it happens with the audio perceptual features domain, it can be seen as a multi-level and structured issue (see Figure 1.2 and Figure 2.6. However, no formal structured analysis of gestures has been carried out explicitly, in contrast to some more score-related approaches adopted in the audio perceptual domain (see previous Section). We believe that the main cause is that the extraction of instrumental gesture descriptors has been mostly applied for real time synthesis. Such an structured approach would surely need of a score-alignment component (maybe in combination with an audio analysis component).

An constraining factor for the extraction of instrumental gestures from the physical action domain is the intrusion caused by the measurement devices, or even the complete impossibility (for instance the singing voice). A number of studies dealt with the measurement of bowed string instrument physical movements (more focused to one of the future directions of the applications of the research proposed here), which resulted less intrusive. Less suited a priori for being applied for signal-based models than for physical model based synthesis, the real time extraction of violin bowing parameters has been used for driving both kinds of synthesizers.

Several authors measured physical actions from performances, but only a few used the information for inducing playing techniques, as it is the case of the work by Rasamimanana [Ras05]. In this work, it used an "augmented violin", i.e., an acoustic instrument with added gesture capture capabilities to control electronic processes based on accelerometers placed in the violin bow, in order to

perform gesture analysis on three different bow strokes, *Détaché*, *Martelé*, and *Spiccato*, using this augmented violin. Different features based on velocity and acceleration were considered. A linear discriminant analysis was performed to estimate a minimum number of pertinent features necessary to model these bow stroke classes. They found that the maximum and minimum accelerations of a given stroke were efficient to parameterize the different bow stroke types, as well as differences in dynamics playing, as it is partly shown in Figure 2.18 This work resulted in somehow structured analysis, focused on a instrumental gesture as it is notated in a score, although it is not applied yet for synthesis, because it is not possible to re-render the bowing movements from the extracted statistical parameters. In a posterior article, authors combine video tracking techniques with accelerometers in order to extract bow velocity velocity profiles in different playing techniques [SRB06], while still not quantitatively described.

Figure 2.17: Bow strokes clustering obtained by Rasamimanana [Ras05]. Visualization in terms of the bow acceleration extrema. Each class is represented by one different color.

Intended more as a new instrument used for controlling sound effects than for controlling synthesis (not sample triggering or transformation), author in [You02] describe also the measurement techniques of dynamic bowing parameters.. Conversely, Schoner investigated the instrumental gestures in violin performance applied for real time synthesis [SCG02]. He measured several physical action parameters using an augmented violin. These actions consisted on the bow position

relative to the strings, the bow position relative to the bridge, the finger pressure between forefinger and bow, the finger position on each of the four strings. He additionally obtained the audio signal of the string vibration (see Figure 2.18). He used these features together with audio samples for constructing an original synthesis method based on parameter clustering, and a posterior sample selection and transformation based on such classification. However, no formal description of gestures is carried out due to the on-line oriented synthesis approach it was intended for.

Figure 2.18: Analyzed cello data by Schoner [SCG02]. From the bottom: bow position relative to strings, bow pressure, audio signal, extracted bowing direction, envelope, and harmonic amplitudes.

Some other research efforts have been pushed to the study of gestures not dealing with sound production, but more with expression or conduction. Although not dealing with instrumental gestures as understood in this proposal, authors in [Wan02] present preliminary quantitative results from movement analysis of several clarinet performers with respect to non-obvious or ancillary gestures produced while playing a piece. The comparison of various performances of a

piece by the same clarinetist shows a high consistency of movement patterns. Other studies deal for instance with quantitative analysis of conducting gestures [KW04]. Other studies dealt with video recording analysis of dancing movements in order to obtain some expression information [APMG01].

2.6 Prosody and tonal information in speech

Gesture analysis, understood as time-space trajectories, is of course not only reduced to music, but present in many other disciplines, like automatic optical character recognition or prosody in speech. Speech systems are similar to gesture recognition systems, because all of these systems perform recognition of something that moves, leaving a "trajectory" in space and time. By exploring the literature of speech and handwriting recognition, classification and identification schemes can be studied which might aid in developing a gesture recognition system intended for music performance.

Typical speech recognition systems match transformed speech against a stored representation. Most systems use some form of spectral representation, such as spectral templates or Hidden Markov Models. The information used for such speech recognition systems often does not include contour of fundamental frequency in a parameterized manner, but just some derivatives. However, when the synthesis problem comes into play, speech analysis needs of a extraction of some parameters defining the pitch contour from real data in order to extract expression information and/or learn how to make the synthesized speech more expressive and realistic. In this sense, we understand that the speaker uses some resources in some particular contexts in the same way as the musician makes use of some gestures in some musical contexts. While the context in speech is mainly defined by the words and position in the sentence to be uttered, in music performance it is defined by the score position. The manner in which those gestures (mainly fundamental frequency modulations) are selected and performed in speech might be divided into two main causes: the language, which we claim would correspond to due mainly language constrains (analogous to the instrument practical constrains in music) and own wishes for giving specific expression (analogous to the musicians intentional gestures in music performance).

A very extended model for fundamental frequency contours in speech is the

one proposed by Fujisaki [FO96], which has been successfully applied to different languages. In this model, which includes the mathematical formulation of the generation process pitch contours (one of the major reasons of choosing such parameterization), the shape of a complete utterance is rendered by two components. The first component is the phrase component, while the the second component is the accent group component, modeled by an exponential function, both activated by some commands, as illustrated in Figure 2.19. For identifying parameters, they use an analysis-by-synthesis iterative process, where both the commands and the responses of each of the accent control and phrase control mechanisms are best fitted to a particular utterance.

Figure 2.19: Two component (phrase and accent) description of the fundamental frequency in the Fujisaki model for speech prosody [FO96].

Authors [EC02] in adopted a different approach, modeling each each stress group fundamental frequency contour by means of a cubic Bézier curve, and then learning to predict the parameters defining the curves by means of a big corpus of examples. They decided to use this parameterization mainly due to the flexibility to concatenate each of the contour models and the meaningful manner in which the extracted Bézier control points (see Appendix B) are related to the fundamental frequency contour. This piece-wise technique seems more adapted to a possible description for fundamental frequency or amplitude contours.

Fundamental frequency nuances carry important prosody information for tonal languages, as it is the case of Chinese. Thus some studies have dealt with the extraction of prosody parameters in such cases, or the adaption of their models. This is carried out for Chinese in [SK00], where authors apply soft template tags (Stem-ML) to define the fundamental frequency contours of accent groups and also phrases in a piecewise manner, all defined by the same number

of parameters. Their system includes an algorithm to render the complete fundamental frequency contours from tags given at each accent group and by the interaction between accent groups, also present in the tagged parameters. They obtain the parameters from real data by successive approximation, extending the procedure for synthesizing prosodic styles in in continuous recital spoken queries [SKFL⁺01].

It is interesting how the problem of modeling the fundamental frequency contours in speech has been approached, but an important difference with music performance is the fact that the path along which the instrumentalist or musician has to move already defined. Similar approaches could be investigated towards a structured segmentation of the score, as it is carried out in speech for accent groups. The problem would be that it is not that clear the organization method taking into account the duration of notes in the musical score, other than into beats or groups or beats, as it has been mentioned in previous sections.

2.7 Control possibilities of sound synthesis techniques

2.7.1 Introduction

In this section we will briefly present the basic characteristics of the state of the art sound synthesis methods, analyzing the advantages and disadvantages of each of the approaches in terms of their control possibilities. It is not of our interest to give a thorough and detailed description of the mathematical foundations of each synthesis technique, but a general view of the conceptual characteristics that influence the way they are controlled and how the proposals of this project can help improve their control for natural sound synthesis. For a complete overview of the details of each one of these synthesis techniques, please read [TVK98] and [Smi02b]. First, we will present some classifications already carried out, and a subsequent a broad classification of techniques into signal models and physical models, which we consider more suitable for the approach of modeling instrumental gestures. Then, we will go through each of these two main groups, and highlighting their control possibilities. Although the synthesis

of the singing voice has been approached from different synthesis methodologies, we will treat it separately, pointing out some particular issues that makes very interesting its study and the application of some of the approaches proposed.

2.7.2 Classification

It is a difficult task to define a clear taxonomy to classify existing instrument sound synthesis techniques. Smith [Smi02b] divides synthesis into four categories: *abstract algorithms*, *processing of recorded samples*, *spectral models*, and *physical models*. Abstract algorithms category, as it is understood there, is not of interest when aiming at synthesize an existing instrument or sound, because it is difficult to produce musically pleasing sounds by exploring the parameters of a mathematical expression. The spectral modeling category can be seen as an evolution of processing recorded samples category, because the best way to improve transformations of recordings is to understand their effect on human hearing, and the closest way to the human hearing for representing the sound is by means of a spectral representation. Sampling synthesis transforms samples in time domain and spectral synthesis processes samples in time and frequency domains. The classification found in [Sch04] differentiates sound instrument techniques in those that are based on concatenating samples, called 'concatenative synthesis', and those that are based on parametric models. Both physical and spectral models appear in the same class, called 'parametric synthesis'.

From an instrumental gesture perspective, we decide to make a broader classification that divides them into two main groups: physical models and signal based models. This classification is based on the approach taken when 'imitating' the musical instrument. Physical models are based on analytical formulae describing the acoustic and mechanical behaviour of the musical instrument and its structure, i.e., the sound production mechanisms. They allow input control by means of a reasonable low number of parameters that are directly related to the physical actions applied by performers. In contrast, signal models are based on the perceptual attributes of sound. They are built on top of abstract mathematical structures that store spectral or temporal properties of sound. The input controls for this kind of synthesizers, far away from the production mechanisms of sound, are much closer to the perception of sound, leading to a major

flexibility and simplicity of analysis. These differences make both approaches interesting, depending on the domain from which gestures are 'grasped' (audio perceptual features physical action domain).

2.7.3 Signal model-based synthesis

The signal-based approach models the sound of the instrument itself. Accordingly, it does not make any assumptions on the structure of the musical instrument, only that the generated sound is periodic. Therefore, it can model a wide range of instrument sounds. Since it is a general representation, its parameter estimation can be easily automated. As the structure of the instrument is not modeled, the interaction of the musician cannot be easily taken into account. This means that for instance, in the case of the violin, for different bow forces or velocities, different parameter sets are required for re-synthesis. Practically for a single note, the analysis procedure has to be run for all the different playing styles that a player can produce, and a large amount of data has to be stored or transmitted. As it treats the notes separately, the interaction of the different notes cannot be easily modeled, thus sampling different articulations results normally in a better choice. We can divide the signal model-based synthesis approaches into two main groups, attending to the domain in which processing is carried out: sample-based synthesis and spectral modeling synthesis.

Sample-based synthesis

It has been traditionally understood as based on playback and transformations of recorded samples in the time domain, as an evolution of tape-based "musique concrète". The level of realism and sound quality in individual samples is the highest possible, because there is no synthetic sound produced but recordings. The problems come out when the samples are played in sequence: all the transitions and nuances (so important in musical phrasing and expression) that are not stored in the database, will be missing. Moreover, it is difficult to transform a sample without altering its perceptual properties. Although recent sophisticated synthesizers using spectral representations of sounds are also called sample-based because they are based on 'sampling' sounds and storing them as sequences of spectra to which apply transformations. Concatenative synthesis

[Sch00] [Sch04], understood as such, could be also included in this category.

A clear example of sample-based synthesis, showing the disadvantages of this approach in terms of flexibility of control, is the commercial software synthesizer 'Vienna Symphonic Library'⁶. For constructing the database of samples, every instrument has been meticulously recorded, playing a big number of articulations. Variations include notes of various lengths, all kinds of dynamics (accents, crescendos/decrescendos, etc.), and effects such as tremolo strings and flutter-tongued winds and brass, trills, rolls, etc., all recorded at various tempi. In spite of the high quality of the samples and the great variety, the expressivity and naturalness is limited. In order to make possible to sequence realistic performances, it is needed a long time to learn how to select samples and their combinations in each situation, while no transformations are allowed. Moreover, the concatenation of recordings is sometimes noticeable.

Spectral models

Spectral models those that rely on the spectral properties of the sound and store a representation of the spectrum in frame along time. Spectral properties are considered to be constant during the frame duration, and thus the sound perceptual properties. This definition covers a wide range of possible models and representations, as for instance phase vocoder [Fla66], sinusoidal model [MQ86], phase locked vocoder [Puc95], and spectral modeling synthesis (SMS) [SS90]. The advantage and success of these techniques resides in the well-defined analysis-transformation-resynthesis techniques, that allow high quality transformations and sound fidelity. It is therefore the most common tendency to mix the ideas of sample-based synthesis and spectral models to sample notes/phrases/articulations from a real instrument. However, some problems derived from these 'sampling' could be partly solved by taking into account how both audio perceptual parameters, and sound producing gestures evolve during performance, and by means of a proper matching between the two domains (see Figure 1.2). Since it is not always easy to measure instrumental gestures in the physical action domain, the use of a signal model-based synthesis approach, for which it is easy to extract audio perceptual parameters (like it is the case for

⁶<http://www.vsl.co.at/>

spectral models) to control it

Authors in [BL03] and [Bon01] present a concatenative sample-based singing voice synthesizer that stores spectral representation and transform and concatenates samples. The ideas presented resulted in the commercial application 'Vocaloid', by Yamaha. Each of the possible articulations for each language are sampled at different dynamics, tempi and fundamental frequencies, resulting in a very high quality and realistic voice model. However, the nuances of amplitude and fundamental frequency during performance are not captured because it is timbre-oriented. Any expressive resource (attacks, transitions, vibratos) must be tuned manually. We understand that the study and characterization of sound-producing gestures (in addition of the timbre itself) for constructing the database will surely mean a significant improvement in terms of sample selection (matching annotated gestures with rendered ones) and transformation.

Another commercial application based on spectral representations of sound is the software Synful⁷ [Lin01], which aims at the reconstruction of expressive solo instrument performances from simple MIDI input. Real instrument recordings are segmented into a database of attack, sustain, release, and transition units of varying sub-types. The samples from the database, expressed as a two-component model, are retrieved based on of rules that look for some contextual information extracted from the MIDI score. The two-component model is based on slow and rapid variations of fundamental frequency and amplitude contours. While the slow variations are governed by a filtered version of the input MIDI version, the rapid variations are stored in the database. Thus retrieving the proper samples from the database will imply getting the proper rapid variations for that context. Then, on one hand, the relative amplitude of harmonics for each timbre are computed from the amplitude and fundamental frequency values for each frame by using neural networks. The noisy component of the spectrum is retrieved directly from the database. Again, the expressivity is limited to the articulation and phrasing present in the database, while no expressive meaningful transformations to the samples are applied.

⁷<http://www.synful.com/>

2.7.4 Physical model-based synthesis

Physical model-based synthesis is founded on mathematical models that describe the physical acoustics of instrumental sound production. They are not only used for simulating the sound-producing mechanisms of existing instruments, but also for creating sounds of fanciful instruments that would otherwise be impossible to build. Physical model-based based synthesis relies on the production mechanisms of sound and not on the perception of sound. Since it makes assumptions about the instrument it models, the parameter estimation cannot be completely automated, so at least the model structure has to be determined by the user. As the model structure already describes the main features of the instrument, only small numbers of parameters are needed, and by modifying some of these parameters produce perceptually meaningful results. For example, in violin performance, the user controls the bow force, rather than the loudness of a single partial, and the instrument reacts in a way as a real violin would do. Therefore, only one parameter set is required, since the different playing styles according to the interaction of the musician will be the result of applying appropriate input parameters. As it describes the physical structure, the interaction of the different model parts are also taken into account. A clear advantage of physical modeling synthesis is the fact that the input controls are directly related to the physical actions (they are actually a copy), so that they do not need to be 'induced' from an analysis of the audio stream coming out from the instrument during performance. Several mathematical techniques have been used, among which we could highlight vibrating mass-spring networks and digital waveguides. For a detailed overview of physical model-based synthesis techniques, please refer to [Smi02a] and [TVK98].

Modeling acoustic instruments by means of physical models has had much more success for the case of excitation-instantaneous musical instruments, since the interaction of the musician is more limited and easy to represent. Physical models are theoretically the most powerful methods, in the sense that if we could know the exact psycho-acoustic behavior of an instrument we could synthesize its sound production. But it would be computationally expensive, and even if we could find a trustworthy model computationally cheap, we would need to control each of the parameters. Getting a realistic and expressive sound results in a highly difficult task, sometimes requiring the same interface to control it

as for the acoustic instrument counterpart, that is, the instrument itself. In case such an interface is not available, or either for off-line synthesis, one of the main problems of physical modeling is how to extract and control expressive performance parameters and used them as input controls, since it is not always possible to measure the physical actions applied to the instrument (think of the singing voice) during performance. In this sense, physical models have been traditionally rather unsuccessful from a musical point of view. Still, there are a number of attempts to control physical model-based synthesizers from the input controls of an interface representing the real one, or either by using directly measured actions from an augmented instrument, as it is the case of [You02] and posterior works, where dynamic parameters of violin bowing are extracted. However, the success of such set ups falls into doubt due to the lack of sound quality/fidelity of the mathematical approaches in which physical models are based, or either because of the mapping strategies that have been chosen.

2.7.5 Mixed approaches

The combination of signal models and physical models in order to build realistic mixed/hybrid synthesis models has not been yet studied in depth. There are some attempts to synthesize instrument sounds that do not fit into the sections above, because they combine features from signal models and from physical models. Authors present in [OG03] a hybrid model of a flute, combining signal and physical models. They base their model on the classical exciter-resonator approach of physical models. For modeling the resonator, it is used a physical model of the structure of the instrument, by means of digital waveguides. For modeling the source, they use a signal model based on spectral representation. In [JS01] physical controls from a violin bow are matched with parameters of a spectral model in order to synthesized spectra in real time. Their approach is based on a mixture density estimator around local models (clusters given the input physical actions) for predicting the time-series values of the spectral parameters of the synthesized tones.

2.7.6 Singing voice synthesis

Since the first use of digital technology in singing voice synthesis in 1961 by John Kelly at Bell Labs, who programmed a computer to sing a song using the Linear Predictive Coding (LPC) technique, some commercial software products for singing synthesis have been released. It is not until the appearance of Yamaha's 'Vocaloid' [BL03] in 2003, that a high quality synthesized voice can be used for music performance, at least as an acceptably good chorus set. Detailed reviews of singing voice synthesis can be further read at [Geo04] and [Coo96].

Singing voice synthesis has been an active research field for almost fifty years [Coo96]. Traditionally, the voice has been modeled as a linear system consisting of one or more sources and a set of filters that shape the spectrum of the sources. The sound source can be a periodic signal, a noisy signal, or a mixture of both, and the set of filters can be regarded as the vocal tract filters. The resulting spectrum is characterized by resonant peaks called formants. Thus a vocal synthesizer has to allow the control of the resonant peaks of the spectrum and of the source parameters. With regard to the synthesis models used in singing voice synthesis, they can be classified into the same two groups: signal models (specifically featuring spectral representation), which can be viewed as based on perceptual mechanisms; and physical models, which can be viewed as based on production mechanisms. Any of these two models might be considered as suitable as the other, depending on the specific requirements of the application, or may even be combined to take advantage of both approaches.

The main benefit of using physical models is that the parameters used in the model are closely related to the ones a singer uses to control his/her own vocal system. As such, some knowledge of the real-world mechanism can be introduced in the design. The model itself can provide intuitive parameters if it is constructed with the intention that it sufficiently matches the physical system. Conversely, such a system usually has a large number of parameters for the case of the singing voice. This turns the mapping of the controls of the production mechanism to the final output, and so to the perceived quality by the listener, into something not trivial [Coo91]. On the other hand, signal models are closely related to some aspects of the human perceptual mechanism. Changes in the parameters of a spectral model can be more easily mapped to a change of

sensation in the listener. Yet parameter spaces yielded by these systems are not necessarily the most natural ones for manipulation. The methods based on signal models include frequency modulation, vocoder and sinusoidal models. Acoustic tube models are an example of physical models. Linear Predictive Coding (LPC) and formant synthesizers can be considered as signal models and also as pseudo-physical, not strictly physical because of the source/filter decomposition they use.

Vocaloid [BL03] [Bon01] is a sample-based synthesizer that relies on the retrieval and transformation of articulations previously recorded in a studio. For each language, the totality of possible diphonemes is recorded at different tempi, loudness and fundamental frequency, stored and appropriately labeled. Then, the selection of samples is carried out by matching the input lyrics and target score, based on a minimization of a transformation cost function that considers speed (or tempo), fundamental frequency and loudness. One of the main problems encountered to get a realistic and expressive sound synthesis is precisely the micro-intonation and expressive gestures used (e.g. vibratos, legato/staccato articulations, scoop transitions, etc. For improving the expressivity of the synthesized voice, the user is able to add manually some of these resources from a database, or even to modify the contours of amplitude or fundamental frequency by hand.

Driving singing voice performance synthesis by a human voice has been studied in [JBB06], and showed to be an interesting approach. Knowing the lyrics to be performed, the system uses phonetic segmentation of the input voice as an alignment for constructing a score. In this score which will serve for sample selection from the database each note onset corresponds to a input vowel onset, understood as a peak in a temporal function representing timbre variability. Fundamental frequency and amplitude are averaged within each note limit, in order to retrieve the samples from the database, consisting in the diphonemes matching the phonetic segmentation of the input voice. Then, these diphonemes are concatenated, and transformed in amplitude and pitch space for matching the input contours.

Thus, there is a lot of room for improvement in this research area, and naturalness is one of the keywords for the work to be done. Moreover, it seems that one of the main issues behind singing voice synthesis is to offer not only qual-

ity but also flexible and musically meaningful control over the vocal sound. In that sense, we may think of applications where impossible singing voices can be synthesized or where existing voices can be enhanced. In order to build realistic singing voice synthesizers, we believe that it is needed an structured quantitative characterization of the contours of fundamental frequency and loudness, and also extend the study to other expressive voice parameters, such as brightness, whisper, or roughness.

Chapter 3

Initial Contributions

3.1 Introduction

In this Section we give a detailed review of the main contributions of the research carried out by the author in the direction of characterization of instrumental gestures. Contributions are divided into the two research projects/groups in which the author has been already partly involved: the prOmusic project and the voice processing group of the MTG, both introduced in Chapter 1. All contributions, reflected in conference articles, are cited in the following subsections. From the contributions to the prOmusic project, we classify them into *description of instrumental gestures* and *application of the analysis of instrumental gestures*, both dealing with audio analysis approach of instrumental gestures. Instrumental gestures are understood here as amplitude profiles of single notes or note-to-note articulation amplitude properties. The contribution to the Voice and Audio Processing team is dealing with the analysis and quantitative description of singing voice articulation, focused mainly on fundamental frequency profiles, including a small experiment for validating the model.

We outline next an abstract for each one of the four contributions. Then, we review in depth the contents of the two publications dealing with automatic characterization of gestures in the audio analysis domain: *Automatic characterization of dynamics and articulation of expressive monophonic recordings* and *Modeling musical articulation gestures in singing voice performance*. Other publications by the author are cited in Appendix C.

3.1.1 Contributions to the prOmusic project

Within the scope of the project prOmusic, three main contributions are reported in the context of this proposal:

- **Description of instrumental gestures:**
 - **Automatic characterization of dynamics and articulation of expressive monophonic recordings.** We describe a method to automatically extract a set of features from the audio signal that are related to musical expressivity, more concretely to dynamics and articulation. We define a description scheme based on intra-note segmentation into attack, sustain, release and transition segments, and a subsequent amplitude (note envelope and note-to-note transition) and pitch contour (note-to-note transition) characterization. Then, we present a series of algorithms to automatically perform intra-note segmentation and extract some features related to expressivity. We evaluate the performance of the methods for intra-note segmentation and feature extraction over a saxophone database of jazz standards and other recordings presenting expressive resources.
PUBLICATION: "Automatic characterization of dynamics and articulation of expressive monophonic recordings". E. Maestre, E. Gomez, *Proceedings of the AES 118th Convention*, Barcelona, Spain. 2005.
- **Application of the analysis of instrumental gestures:**
 - **Intra-note features prediction model for jazz saxophone performance.** We outline an approach to investigate musical expressive performance based on inductive machine learning. In particular, we focus on the study of variations on intra-note features (e.g. attack, sustain, release) that a saxophone interpreter introduces in order to expressively perform a Jazz standard. The study of these features is intended to build on our current system which predicts expressive deviations on note duration, note onset and note energy. This work is considered as a preliminar application of the dynamics and articulation description obtained in the previous work.

PUBLICATION: "Intra-note features prediction model for jazz saxophone performance". R. Ramirez, A. Hazan, E. Maestre. *Proceedings of the International Computer Music Conference*, Barcelona, Spain. 2005.

- **Using concatenative synthesis for expressive saxophone performance.** We present a concatenative sample-based saxophone synthesizer using an induced performance model intended for expressive synthesis. The system consists on three main parts. The first part provides the analysis of saxophone expressive performance recordings and the extraction of descriptors related to different temporal levels. With the obtained descriptors and the analyzed samples, we construct an annotated sample database extracted directly from the performances. For the second part, we use the annotations to induce a performance model capable of predicting some features related to expressivity. In the third part, the predictions of the performance model are used to retrieve the most suitable note samples for each situation, and transform and concatenate them following the input score and the induced model. In this work, we intended to use information about instrumental gestures, which has been extracted automatically, in order to construct a basic synthesis application in which different notes are chosen depending on some musical context.

PUBLICATION: "Using concatenative synthesis for expressive saxophone performance". E. Maestre, A. Hazan, R. Ramirez, A. Perez. *Proceedings of the International Computer Music Conference*, New Orleans, USA. 2006.

3.1.2 Contribution to the Voice Processing Group at the MTG

In the context of singing voice synthesis, one of the major topics of the Voice Processing Group at the MTG, a recent contribution is detailed next:

- **Modeling musical articulation gestures in singing voice performance.** We present a procedure to automatically describe musical articulation gestures used in singing voice performances. We detail a method to

characterize temporal evolution of fundamental frequency and energy contours by a set of piece-wise fitting techniques. Based on this, we propose a meaningful parameterization that allows reconstructing contours from a compact set of parameters at different levels. We test the characterization method by applying it to fundamental frequency contours of manually segmented transitions between adjacent notes, and train several classifiers with manually labeled examples. We show the recognition accuracy for different parameterizations and levels of representation.

PUBLICATION: "Modeling musical articulation gestures in singing voice performance". E. Maestre, J. Bonada, O. Mayor. *Proceedings of the AES 121st Convention*, San Francisco, USA. 2006.

3.2 Characterization of dynamics and articulation of expressive saxophone recordings

This study has been developed in the context of a system intended to learn and transform expressive patterns from saxophone recordings of jazz standards [RHGM04]. Possible applications of this system include performer and performance understanding and modeling, as well as expressive audio transformations and synthesis [SX98]. In order to analyze the expressivity of an audio phrase, we first define a structured set of features related to expressivity (i.e. a description scheme) and then we find methods to extract these features in an automatic way. Previous work in [GGAA03] was devoted to extract a melodic description intended to analyze mainly timing deviations and insertions/deletions of notes. This melodic description codes information related to the exact time location of each of the notes of the melody. Here, we extend this melodic description to represent two important factors for music performance: dynamics and articulation. Other works in [DPD98],[DR98] studied instrument specific envelope for synthesis, and dynamics and timing respectively.

Dynamics is usually defined as the intensity or volume with which notes are played. Articulation refers primarily to the degree to which a performer detaches individual notes from one another in practice (e.g. staccato and legato). In this study we present a method to automatically analyze dynamics and articulation

from monophonic audio recordings of solo phrases, based in studying the energy envelope and fundamental frequency contour of the audio signal.

3.2.1 Description scheme

The proposed description scheme, which extends the scheme already presented in [GGAA03], is summarized in Figure 3.1. We define descriptors related to different temporal scales:

- Some features are defined as *instantaneous* or related to an analysis frame, such as energy, fundamental frequency [Can98] and spectral centroid.
- We also obtain intra-note/inter-note segment features, i.e. descriptors attached to a certain intra-note segment: attack, sustain and release (considering an ADSR model presented in [Ber76]) or transition segment. We consider that the proposed features can set up a simple but concise dynamics and articulation model adapted to our application context. The procedure for the extraction of these features, which is the main focus of this work, is explained in next Section.
- Note features or descriptors attached to a certain note are also extracted (already outlined in [GGAA03]).
- Finally, some global features are related to the whole performance, such as tempo or key.

3.2.2 Feature extraction

The basis of this study is the analysis of the energy envelope and fundamental frequency contour of the audio signal in order to extract features related to articulation and dynamics. The audio signal is divided into analysis frames, and some low-level frame descriptors are computed. Then, note segmentation is performed, extracting note features in order to obtain a melodic description. Finally, we carry out intra-note segmentation and characterize each intra-note and inter-note segments.

Figure 3.1: Description scheme used for the characterization dynamics and articulation of expressive saxophone recordings

Melodic description

The first step consists of the extraction of a melodic description from the performance. This procedure, previous basis for this work, is explained in [GGAA03] and includes the extraction of low-level descriptors (energy, fundamental frequency and spectral centroid), the segmentation into notes and the computation of some note and global descriptors.

Intra-note segmentation

The proposed intra-note segmentation method is based on the study of the energy envelope contour of the note. Once onsets and offsets are located, we study the instantaneous energy values of the analysis frames corresponding to each note. This study is carried out by analyzing the envelope curvature and characterizing its shape, in order to estimate the limits of the intra-note segments.

When observing the note energy envelopes from the saxophone recordings, we identify that there are usually three segments (attack, sustain and release [Ber76]) needed to conform a description that fits the model schematically represented in Figure 3.2. We discarded the decay segment due to the general characteristics of the notes within the performances.

In order to extract these three characteristic segments, we study the smoothed derivatives in a similar way that presented in [Jen99a], where partial amplitude

Figure 3.2: Schematic view of the proposed energy envelope-based intra-note segmentation.

envelopes are modeled for isolated sounds. The main difference is that we analyze the notes in their musical context, rather than isolated. In addition, since our context is related to expressive patterns extraction by means of artificial intelligence techniques [GGAA03] and not a priori with complex synthesis, the model is simplified (in order to induce expression rules [RHGM04]), and only three linear segments are considered. Moreover, instead of studying the contribution of all the partials, we obtain general intensity information from the total energy envelope characteristic. The procedure is carried out as follows.

Considering the energy envelope as a differentiable function over time, the points of maximum curvature can be considered as the local maximum variations of the first derivative of the signal energy (second derivative extremes), that is, the local maxima or minima of the second derivative.

Due to the characteristics of the audio signal, the energy envelope must be previously smoothed by low-pass filtering, since there are typically too many second derivative extrema. Several smoothing steps are carried out in order to find a good cut-off frequency of the smoothing filter. The smoothed envelope should not differ much to the original one, in order to avoid the loss of localization caused by the filtering effect. Thus, for each smoothing step, the error e_m at smoothing step m between original and current envelope is computed. This is carried out by means of (3.1), where N is the length of the envelope in frames,

env is the original envelope, env_m is the smoothed envelope at step m , and \overline{env} is the average energy of the current note.

$$e_m = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{1 \leq k \leq N} \frac{|env(k) - env_m(k)|^2}{\overline{env}} \quad (3.1)$$

Starting from a low cut-off frequency f_{0init} , this frequency is increased each smoothing step m until the error e_m gets lower than a certain threshold γ_{th} . This threshold has been empirically selected, as it will be explained in next section. Then, we compute the three first derivatives of the last smoothed envelope. Frame positions and corresponding y -values of second derivative extremes are stored. Afterwards, these characteristic points are sorted by the second derivative modulus, and the n highest positions are selected to build up the set of characteristic points F . Of course, when the total number of third derivative zero-crossings is less than n , the set is F shortened. In next section, we evaluate the influence of both γ_{th} and n on the algorithm performance. Both note onset and offset are added as characteristic points to the set F . The slope defined by each pair of consecutive characteristic points on the envelope is computed (3.2), where i and j denote frame positions. A minimum slope duration (measured in frames) Δfr is defined relative to the note duration as the five per cent of the note length N for excluding the possible too high valued slopes near the note limits.

$$\nabla i, j \in F \text{ such as } i \leq j + \Delta fr, s_{i,j} = \frac{env_m(j) - env_m(i)}{j - i} \quad (3.2)$$

Finally, the two pairs of points defining, respectively, the most positive and most negative slope values from the remaining slopes after discarding are extracted. The end of the attack segment f_{AE} is defined as the frame position corresponding to second point of the maximum slope s_M , while the start of the release segment position f_{RB} is defined as the first point of the minimum slope s_m . This is stated in (3.3) and (3.4) and depicted in Figure 3.3.

$$s_M = s_{i_M, j_M} = \max(s_{i,j}), f_{AE} = j_M \quad (3.3)$$

$$s_m = s_{i_m, j_m} = \min(s_{i, j}),, f_{RB} = i_m \quad (3.4)$$

Figure 3.3: Original and smoothed envelopes of a real sax note extracted from the recordings for a value of $\gamma_{th}=0.05$ (top figure, solid and dashed thin lines, respectively). Selected characteristic points are denoted with a square within extremes of the second derivative of the smoothed envelope (bottom figure)

The attack is defined as the segment between the note onset and the end of the most positive of the computed slopes, while the release segment is defined as the segment between the start of the most negative of the computed slopes and the note offset. Sustain is restricted to the remaining segment. When the end of attack and the start of release limits of a note coincide, it is considered that

the note does not present sustain segment. The algorithm can be schematically written as in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1 Energy-based intra-note segmentation

```

Set  $f_{0init}$ ,  $\gamma_{th}$  and  $n$ 
Extract energy envelope
 $f_0 \leftarrow f_{0init}$ 
 $e_m \leftarrow \infty$ 
while  $e_m > \gamma_{th}$  do
  Increase  $f_0$ 
  Smooth the envelope applying LP filter with cutoff at  $f_0$ 
  Compute  $e_m$ 
end while
Compute derivatives of last smoothed envelope
Locate 2nd derivative modulus maxima
Get the  $n$  positions with highest 2nd derivative modulus
Discard too short segments
Compute segment slopes and sort them
Assign attack-end to max-slope segment's right limit
Assign release-start to min-slope segment's left limit

```

Intra-note segment characterization

Once we have found the intra-note segment limits, we describe each one by its duration (absolute and relative to note duration), start and end times, initial and final energy values (absolute and relative to note maximum) and slope. For the sustain segment, we compute some vibrato and tremolo descriptors [HB98], consisting on start and end times, depth and rate. We tried several methods for estimating low-frequency modulations, obtaining better results by studying zero-crossings of the smoothed fundamental frequency and energy envelope derivatives.

Transition segment characterization

When there is no silence between two consecutive notes, we consider a note transition segment starting at the first note's release and finishing at the attack of the following one. Both the energy envelope and the fundamental frequency

Figure 3.4: Energy envelope of a real excerpt with intra-note segment and transition limits marked.

contour during transitions are studied in order to extract descriptors related to articulation.

In addition to the characterization of release and attack segments of the involved notes, we measure the energy envelope minimum position t_c (see Figure 3.5) with respect to the transition duration as (3.5). This descriptor might be useful when reconstructing amplitude envelopes during transitions.

$$E_{TPOS_{min}} = \frac{t_c}{t_{end} - t_{init}} \quad (3.5)$$

In order to extract a descriptor indicating how sharply detached two notes were, we compute a legato descriptor by means of two simple methods. For the first method, we join start and end points on the energy envelope contour by means of a line L_t that would represent the smoothest case of detachment. Then, we compute both the area A_2 below energy envelope and the area A_1 between energy envelope and the joining line L_t and define our legato descriptor as shown in (3.6).

$$LEG_1 = \frac{A_1}{A_1 + A_2} = \frac{\int_{t_{init} \leq t \leq t_{end}} (L_t(t) - E_{XX}(t)) dt}{\int_{t_{init} \leq t \leq t_{end}} L_t(t) dt} \quad (3.6)$$

For the second method, we compute the ratio between the local minimum of the energy envelope within transition E_{Tmin} and the minimum of the values of energy envelope at transition boundaries E_{RT} and E_{LT} , as it is shown in (3.7).

$$LEG_2 = \frac{E_{Tmin}}{\min(E_{TR}, E_{LT})} \quad (3.7)$$

After observing fundamental frequency contours from the recordings, pitch steps are considered to be linear for this study ((see Figure 3.5), being characterized by measuring width and translation with respect to the position of the energy envelope minimum and the transition length. Pitch step center time t_{FC} and width W_{PT} (see Figure 3.5) are measured by finding the boundaries of pitch steps studying pitch derivative along the transition. Note that pitch step width W_{PT} is suitable for enrich a legato descriptor in terms of fundamental frequency description.

Figure 3.5: Schematic view of the transition segment characterization.

3.2.3 Case study

In this section, we show some evaluation results of the algorithm used for intra-note segmentation, and of both intra-note and transition segments characterization. For this study we have used an audio database consisting on five saxophone jazz standards played by a professional performer at eleven different tempi around the nominal one. Other saxophone recordings presenting expressive resources have been also used.

Intra-note segmentation

The results of the intra-note segmentation algorithm are compared to manual annotations, in order to evaluate its performance. This has been carried out with a set of 100 notes from our jazz performance recordings, where both the end of attack and the beginning of release have been marked. We compare the duration of the attack and release segments with the data extracted from the automatic segmentation for different values of intra-note segmentation algorithm parameters γ_{th} and n (see Section 3.2.2).

We compute a segment relative mean duration error $RMDE$, by means of (3.8), where N is the total number of notes, d_{RELSm} is the manually labeled duration for the corresponding segment relative to the current note duration, and d_{RELSa} is the automatically extracted duration, also relative to corresponding note duration.

$$RMDE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{1 \leq k \leq N} | d_{RELSm}(k) - d_{RELSa}(k) | \quad (3.8)$$

The results obtained are shown in Table 3.1 and Table 3.2 for the attack and release segments respectively. They reveal reliable algorithm performance, and help in the selection of some parameters.

The increase of error for the case of release segment might be due to the fact that the algorithm sometimes assigns the whole sustain segment to be part of the release and vice versa (failing in detecting the presence of sustain segment leads to a high error), while for the attack segment there is less ambiguity.

$RMDE_{attack}$				
n	$\gamma_{th}=0.03$	$\gamma_{th}=0.05$	$\gamma_{th}=0.07$	$\gamma_{th}=0.09$
4	0.079	0.079	0.051	0.056
6	0.080	0.080	0.053	0.068
8	0.084	0.084	0.054	0.068

Table 3.1: Values of attack segment relative mean duration error $RMDE_{attack}$ for different values of γ_{th} and n used in the intra-note segmentation algorithm.

$RMDE_{release}$				
n	$\gamma_{th}=0.03$	$\gamma_{th}=0.05$	$\gamma_{th}=0.07$	$\gamma_{th}=0.09$
4	0.122	0.137	0.134	0.156
6	0.084	0.107	0.104	0.157
8	0.073	0.091	0.112	0.156

Table 3.2: Values of release segment relative mean duration error $RMDE_{release}$ for different values of γ_{th} and n used in the intra-note segmentation algorithm.

Intra-note and transition segment chracterization

Once intra-note segmentation gives accurate results, the validity of the feature extraction method is tested. Regarding dynamics, we measured the error between the real energy envelope and the one obtained by approximating each intra-note segment by means of a linear segment (see Figure 3.4). This error, that we call the approximation error e_{APPR} , is computed as (3.9), where N is the number of frames of the current note, E_{REAL} is the real energy envelope of the note and E_{APPR} is the approximated energy envelope.

$$e_{APPR} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{1 \leq k \leq N} \frac{|E_{REAL}(k) - E_{APPR}(k)|}{E_{REAL}} \quad (3.9)$$

We have computed the average value of the approximation error e_{APPR} for 1000 notes, using different values of the intra-note segmentation algorithm parameters γ_{th} and n (Section 3.2.2). As it can be observed in Figure 3.6, the error threshold γ_{th} helps much more in finding a minimum, while the influence of the number of points n is not so clear. Therefore, it is easy to find a compromise between the approximation error and the validity of the intra-note segmentation (Section 3.2.2).

In terms of articulation, we have measured the relevance of the legato de-

Figure 3.6: Mean approximation error e_{APPR} for different values of γ_{th} and n used in intra-note segmentation algorithm.

scriptors for the discrimination between two different expressive intentions. For doing so, a skilled saxophonist has been asked to play some phrases or excerpts articulating notes in both the extremes of *legato* and *staccato*, obtaining a high correlation between the computed descriptors and the expressive intentions, as it is shown in Figure 3.7.

3.2.4 Conclusion and further work

We have presented a description scheme for expressive performance of monophonic audio recordings. We have outlined a method to extract a set of expressive descriptors, in terms of energy and fundamental frequency, from saxophone expressive recordings. We have evaluated some of our results, for which our methods have shown to provide good reliability.

For intra-note and transition segments, in addition to analyzing other spectral descriptors, parametric curve models are to be extracted instead of linear segments, being very useful depending on the application and the accuracy and/or complexity of the model to be obtained. In terms of fundamental frequency contour description, a deeper study is still necessary in order to obtain reliable results. Some other instruments should be tried, and we surely have to modify and improve our methods for being as versatile and accurate as possible.

Figure 3.7: Schematic view of the computed *legato* descriptors for a saxophone excerpt performed by means of extreme legato/staccato articulations.

Although it is still in the analysis stage, we intend to build a performance model, in order to be able to reproduce the performance naturalness and/or expression, or even to study and identify different intentions or styles. Other applications may also include expressive MIDI mapping for existing synthesizers, as well as the extraction of key information for the development of new synthesizers.

3.3 Modeling articulation gestures in singing voice performances

Restricting articulation gestures in singing voice to be mainly conveyed by pitch and amplitude modulations, we present here a quantitative characterization of fundamental frequency and energy contours of manually segmented articulations, understood as note-to-note transitions. We model contours by a set of piece-wise fitting techniques and a meaningful parameterization, consisting in linear approximation and Bézier spline approximation, both with several levels of representation. One important aim of the characterization method is the possibility to be used both in recognition and synthesis stages, so that still keeping a reduced

number of parameters, contours can be reconstructed with enough accuracy. As an experiment, we use the characterization method for the classification of transitions in terms of fundamental frequency contours of manually labeled transitions between adjacent notes. We show the recognition accuracy for three different classification methods and four different parameterizations.

First, we give some details about the database we used for our experiments, and we describe shortly how we prepare our data. In Section 3.3.2, we give the details of our description procedure. After that, an experiment on transition classification is reported in Section 3.3.3. Finally, some conclusions and further work are pointed out in Section 3.3.4.

3.3.1 Data preprocessing

For carrying out this work, we used a small database of 4 popular song excerpts, performed by different trained singers. For each excerpt we have the voice solo recording and its corresponding original score, stored in MIDI format. The segmentation has been carried out as follows. First, the performances have been automatically segmented into notes by means of an alignment to the original score. In a second step, note-to-note transition articulations are manually segmented following well defined criteria. The total number of transitions is 332. We used the software SMSTools¹ for carrying out the automatic alignment and segmentation, and also for the extraction of energy and fundamental frequency frame-by-frame contours, hop-size of 512 samples. We express fundamental frequency in *cents* and energy in *dB*. We also smoothed contours and applied some preprocessing them in order to avoid some discontinuities and modulations due to unvoiced consonants.

Note segmentation

Performance recordings are automatically segmented into notes using Hidden Markov Models (HMMs) with note duration models, similar to the method described in [CLB99], but including some heuristic rules [MBL06]. One of the principles of this segmentation algorithm is the assumption that the singer does

¹developed in the Music Technology Group, Universitat Pompeu Fabra, as an internal project

not make use of ornaments, nor consolidation of notes. Once note boundaries are obtained, they are revised manually in order to correct possible errors of the algorithm. Then, transitions are manually segmented looking mainly at the fundamental frequency contour and note boundaries. Roughly, the criteria used can be summarized as the following:

- We consider a transition as a portion of sound shared by two successive notes.
- We assume that the singer is not inserting silences between notes that appeared together in the original score.
- The note boundary is always included in the transition segment.
- Fundamental frequency values at transition boundaries are close to the quantized MIDI pitch of the notes involved.
- Fundamental frequency discontinuities due to phonetics (see Section 3.3.1) are always included in the transition.

An example of transition segmentation is depicted in Figure 3.8, where we can see the audio waveform and note segmentation at the top, and pitch contour and transition segmentation at the bottom.

Contour preparation

The gross contour of the voice pitch, which we may view as a sort of macro-intonation, is decided by the composer. The singer adds emotion in the domain of the micro-intonation. However, some micro-intonation nuances are not caused by the performer in order to give any expression or style, but by the voice production mechanisms in some phonetic contexts [Sun87]. Thus, singing voice presents some special characteristics, due mainly to phonation, that might be considered in a special way. Some consonants constrain the contours of amplitude and fundamental frequency independently from the intentions of the singer. The most clear example of this is the case of the pronunciation of non-pitched consonants as it is the case of fricatives or plosives. Minor modulations due to voiced consonants have not been taken into account. That is what some people from the speech

Figure 3.8: Screenshot of SMSTools2 and note and transition segmentation. At the top, it is shown the waveform and the note boundaries. At the bottom, one finds both fundamental frequency contour, and transitions represented as a rhombus.

community call the 'micro-prosody' [FO96]. An example showing this effect is depicted in Figure 3.9, where both fundamental frequency and energy contour have been interpolated by means of a cubic Bézier curve (see below for a detailed explanation of the interpolation procedure).

Contour preparation consists of two main steps, carried out for the whole utterance at a time. The first step consists in smoothing contours. For doing so, we filter the contours by applying a gaussian window of a size of five frames. Then, in a second step, we deal with the non-pitched regions by applying some interpolation to the contours. This is carried out for refilling the missing values of fundamental frequency contours and for avoiding important nuances in the energy contour due to pronunciation of unvoiced consonants. We interpolate contours by means of a cubic Bézier curve (see Appendix B). We set the tangents at the initial and final points of the non pitched region as the regression slope of the contour beyond the left and right transition boundaries, respectively. We compute these slopes by taking a small window of three frames before the boundary and after the boundary. Then, we set the position of each inner control point of the cubic Bézier along its corresponding tangent (computed before), at a distance from its outer point equal to the distance between the the limits of the

non-pitched region. We found this approach resulting in well continued contours. Additionally, in order to remove the nuances that the pronunciation of unvoiced consonants produce in the energy envelope, we substitute the energy contour in the non-pitched region by a cubic Bézier computed in the same manner as for fundamental frequency contour (see Figure 3.9).

Figure 3.9: Interpolation of fundamental frequency and energy contours in a non-pitched region. From top to bottom: audio and square indicating an unvoiced consonant, energy contour, and fundamental frequency contour over the quantized MIDI notes. Thick solid lines represent the original contour, while dashed lines represent the interpolation.

3.3.2 Description

When designing the representation procedure, we aimed at getting a meaningful and compact representation that allows to reconstruct easily a contour from the model parameters in order to apply it for synthesis. This led us to decide a piece-wise representation using constrained Bézier splines, always ensuring continuity between adjacent pieces. We discarded the use of polynomials due to the lack of local control. The number of approximating pieces is supplied in advance, so a multi-level representation is obtained for each contour. The fitting algorithm is fed with the normalized contours as they have been extracted from the segmented performances. Before that, a set of landmarks is extracted from each contour by studying extrema and curvature characteristics. During the fitting process, piece-to-piece divisions are allowed to fall only at landmark positions, in order to reduce the search.

Landmark extraction

In order to reduce the computational cost needed for fitting the pieces, we decided to extract a set of landmarks from the contour by studying zero-crossings of smoothed versions of the first and third derivatives. We take this decision based on the assumption that piece-to-piece boundaries will be situated at points with high curvature, thus we look for extrema, both along the contour, and along the second derivative of the contour. Then, during the fitting process, these boundaries are allowed to fall only at landmark positions (see next Section). The procedure is carried out in two steps, performed again to the whole utterance. In a first step, we compute the first three derivatives and find the zero-crossings of the first derivative and third derivative, projecting their positions onto the original envelope. These points on the envelope constitute a first set of landmarks. A detailed explanation of the first procedure of landmark extraction can be found at [MG05].

Then, in a second step, we perform cleaning of landmarks based on their importance given their context. For each landmark, we join a line connecting its predecessor and its successor. Then, we measure the y-axis distance Δy between the landmark and its projection on such line. We discard those landmarks for which Δy is less than a pre-fixed threshold (see Figure 3.10). We have set this

threshold empirically. For the fundamental frequency we set this threshold to be equal to 25 *cents*, i.e. a quarter of a semitone. For the case of energy, we have set the threshold to 1 *dB*.

Figure 3.10: Illustration of the landmark cleaning step for the case of fundamental frequency contour, where two landmarks p_1 and p_2 are considered. Landmark p_1 is kept.

Fitting process

For approximating contours, we chose two different representations from which we are able to reconstruct the approximated contours with different accuracy. We approximate contours by (1) cubic Bézier segments, and (2) linear segments. Each contour (energy and fundamental frequency) is approximated by a finite number of concatenated segments. The number of concatenated segments is supplied in advance. In the second case, which we will explain in detail next, contours are reconstructed by a constrained set of Bézier curves concatenated as explained in Appendix B. The constraints, along with the fitting algorithm, are stated next.

Each concatenation point between segments will correspond to one of the previously extracted landmarks L . The tangents at each junction point are set to present zero-slope, so that the closest inner control points of adjacent curves present the same y-value, and equal to the value of the contour at that landmark. This is illustrated in Figure 3.11 by the two control points $p_{1,3}$ and $p_{2,2}$, conforming the tangent at the landmark L_1 , and the two control points $p_{2,3}$

Figure 3.11: Illustration of the concatenation of several Bézier curves and the tangent constrain at each junction point

and $p_{3,2}$, conforming tangent the landmark L_2 . This is expressed as in equations (3.10) and (3.11), where y represents the y -value of the position af junction points and control points.

$$p_{i+1,2,y} = p_{i,2,y} = L_{i,y} \quad (3.10)$$

$$L_{i,y} = p_{i,4,y} = p_{i+1,1,y} \quad (3.11)$$

For each junction point L_i , we define the x -distance between the control points defining the tangent (and thus how much it is approached by the approximating curve), by means of a strength s_i , being $0 \leq s_i \leq 1$. This only parameter influences both x -distances between junction points L_i and its adjacent control points L_i and its adjacent control points $p_{i-1,3}$ and $p_{i,2}$, i.e, the x -position of the second control point of the $(i + 1)$ - th Bézier curve will range from the x -position of the i - th junction point L_i to the x -value of the next junction point L_{i+1} , depending on the value of S_i . This is expressed for both control sides of the junction point L_i as in equations (3.12) and (3.13).

$$p_{i+1,2,x} = L_{i,x} + S_i(L_{i+1,x} - L_{i+1,x}) \quad (3.12)$$

$$p_{i,3,x} = L_{i,x} - S_i(L_{i,x} - L_{i-1,x}) \quad (3.13)$$

The strengths at the boundaries of the transitions are set to $S_0 = 0.25$ and $S_{N+1} = 0.25$, being N the number of approximating segments. This has been decided empirically with the aim of keeping the number of parameters sufficiently low, and taking into account that these two strengths do not play an important role in the description of the shape.

Then, given the boundaries of the transition, a representation of each approximated contour will depend on the number of segments N used for the approximation, the $N - 1$ junction points L , and the corresponding strengths S . This is expressed as in equation (3.14).

$$\begin{aligned} BC &= f(N, L, S) & (3.14) \\ L &= L_1, \dots, L_N \\ S &= S_1, \dots, S_N \end{aligned}$$

The number of segments used to approximate contours is set in advance, and will serve as an algorithm parameter, setting the level of representation. Then, for fitting each contour, we look for (1) the N positions of the junction points L among the set of extracted landmarks L , and (2) the values of the strengths S applied to each point, that minimize (see equation (3.15)) the squared approximation error ϵ_C of the original contour C .

$$\operatorname{argmin}_{L,S} \epsilon_C(L, S) \quad (3.15)$$

The error approximation will then depend just on the selected junction points L and the corresponding strengths S , as expressed in equation (3.16).

$$\epsilon_C(L, S) = \sum_{1 \leq t \leq T} (BC(L, S, t) - C(t))^2 \quad (3.16)$$

$L, S \text{ fixed}$

In order to find a solution for this optimization problem, we have proceeded with an iterative fitting of both L and S for a given N . The possible values of each pair x and y (one pair defining each junction point) correspond exactly with some of the positions of the already extracted landmarks, so there are finite possibilities where to look for. Conversely, the possible values of each strength S range continuously from 0 to 1, so we have quantized them linearly to ten values in order to be able to find an approximate solution.

As already pointed out above, we also computed a linear approximation of the contours, by setting all strengths S equal to zero and removing them from the search. In such case, we join each of the junction points L by means of linear segments. An example of reconstructed approximation of a fundamental frequency contour for a particular transition is depicted in Figure 3.12, where $N+1=3$ and $N+1=4$ approximating segments have been used, being N the number of landmarks used.

3.3.3 Experiment

As an experiment, we classify transitions depending based on fundamental frequency contour description. By exhaustive observation of fundamental frequency contours of the transitions present in our performance, we observed three main different classes of transitions between notes. We assigned to them the following labels: *normal*, *portamento*, and *scoop*. Next we describe briefly what characterizes these empirically distinguished transition types.

- **Normal:** No extra pitch fluctuation is found, apart from the path from one note to the following during the whole transition.
- **Portamento:** Target pitch is already reached before vowel onset corresponding to note change.

Figure 3.12: Reconstruction of fundamental frequency contour. For the case of 3 concatenated Bézier curves, selected landmarks have been L_2 and L_3 , while for the case of 4 concatenated Bézier curves, L_2 , L_3 , and L_4 have been selected.

- **Scoop:** After the vowel onset, pitch is maintained for several hundreds of milliseconds at a higher or lower value before reaching target pitch.

Before characterizing the segments, we join the outer boundaries of the contour by means of a linear segment with initial and final values equal to the initial and final values of the contour. Then, for each of the selected landmarks, the pitch value of its position is from pitch value of the linear segment at the same position (x -value). This ad-hoc normalizing preprocessing preprocessing is carried out in order to avoid the possible differences among transitions in which origin and target pitch differences are just one semitone, or maybe a complete octave.

Feature vectors consist first in the duration of the transition, and the relative position of the note change. Then, depending on the level of representation, $N - 1$ sub-vectors of features are added, being N the number of segments used for approximate the segment. This subset will consist in the value x and y of the junction points selected by the fitting algorithm detailed above. The x -value is taken as relative to the position of the note change, while for the y -value, we use the normalized values as explained in previous paragraph. For the case of

Classification accuracy (%)			
Representation	NB	MP	k-NN
Lin-2	90.37	91.26	90.96
Lin-3	86.44	90.36	89.45
Bez-2	90.06	90.36	90.67
Bez-3	87.95	88.26	87.65

Table 3.3: Classification accuracy for different classification methods (NB: Naïve Bayes, MP: Multi-layer Perceptron, k-NN: K-Nearest Neighbor) and different levels of representation.

Bézier-spline representation, $N - 1$ strength values are added to each subset.

We trained three different supervised classifiers by means of the tool WEKA [WE99]. The classification methods we used are: Naïve Bayes Classifier (NB), Multi-layer Perceptron Neural Network (MP), and k-Nearest Neighbor Classifier (k-NN). For the MP classifier, we used a hidden layer of twenty perceptron neurons, while for the k-NN classifier we set the number of neighbors to three. No significant improvements were found by modifying algorithm parameters. We used a total of 332 transitions, from which we labeled by hand 258 articulations as *normal*, 59 as *scoop*, and 15 as *portamento*. This leads to a baseline of 73.2%. We show in Table 3.3.3 the recognition accuracy for each one of the three classifiers and four different levels of representation, including two and three linear segments (Lin-2 and Lin-3), and two and three cubic Bézier segments (Bez-2 and Bez-3).

We found high recognition results for all representation levels and classification methods, with no very significant differences. Multi-layer Perceptron classifier (MP) showed to perform slightly better. In terms of representation level, it is found that the more complex is the description, the worst is performance of the classifier. This can be understood as an explanation of the low complexity of the visually perceptual attributes used when looking at pitch contours during manual labeling. If we look into individual class recognition results, it is found high recognition accuracy for both *normal* and *scoop* classes. Conversely, class *portamento* performed poorly in all experiments. We show an example in Table 3.3.3. We can explain this fact by looking at the low number of instances belonging to this class.

k-NN, Bez-2	normal	scoop	portamento
normal	243	10	5
scoop	8	51	0
portamento	12	0	3

Table 3.4: Confusion matrix for the case of k-NN classifier and using two cubic Bézier segments to represent the contour.

3.3.4 Conclusion and future work

We have presented a method for the characterization of fundamental frequency and energy contours of singing voice musical performance articulations. However, this procedure could be used to model the temporal evolution of other performance-related parameters. We have outlined the different steps of data preparation, and the fitting procedure to represent contours by means of several concatenated Bézier curves. We have also shown the results obtained by testing the representation procedure in a transition classification experiment.

The phonetic transcription has not been taken into account, but it is pretended to include it as a way to help in an automatic segmentation process. Moreover, the analysis of micro-prosodic features related to phonetics will definitely help in improving the classification accuracy, since this issue is currently introducing some noise in the contours, which reduces the recognition accuracy. More extended tests, with more different labels and other segments of interest, and dealing also with energy representation are to be carried out. Increasing database size is an important need for improving the results. We have used some adhoc definitions for different transitions types, but the intention is to increase the database and discover transition types by means of clustering techniques.

Possible applications of this modeling procedure, still in a very preliminary stage, are tools for singing education, natural singing voice synthesis, singer identification tasks, and also tools for emulating a reference singer. We plan to transform some real performances, by means of pitch shifting and amplitude scaling, for applying the articulation description obtained by our procedure, and compare the resulting performances to the original recordings.

Chapter 4

Summary and proposed approaches

4.1 Summary

In the first chapter of this proposal, we have introduced the topic of instrumental gestures in excitation-continuous musical instruments, highlighting the clear need of quantitatively describing sound-producing gestures in order to improve musical instrument synthesis. This improvement is to be achieved by explicitly taking into account the interaction between the musician and the instrument, a complex issue not yet addressed in depth for off-line synthesis. Thus the main goal of the research proposed here is to set up a procedure or framework for a structured quantitative description of instrumental gestures. We consider the sequence of instrumental gestures, performed during the interpretation of a score, as continuous time-series contours of parameters taking part both in the interaction with the instrument, and in the perception by the listener. This framework must provide the ways to code such contours by small sets of meaningful parameters, with the aim of being used in a later synthesis stage by reconstructing instrumental gestures from such parameters.

In Chapter 2 we have outlined some relevant research carried out in the field of musical performance from a gestural description perspective, as well some as control techniques for existing synthesis methods. Since instrumental gestures are studied either by measuring the physical actions applied to the instrument, or

by extracting relevant audio perceptual features, we reviewed some techniques used for structuring and representing instrumental gestures in both domains. While for the audio analysis domain more work has been carried out and more structured descriptions have been extracted, the analysis of physical actions have been mainly approached from real-time synthesis view. Several approaches have produced interesting results, mainly in the field of expressive performance analysis. However, each approach has chosen its own methods, while not permitting the interesting reversible properties of an analysis/synthesis framework for instrumental gestures, and not taking into account the synthesis methods to be used. We can conclude from the review that there is a need for a structured and compact method of representing gestures in one or both domains, which allows rendering them from a robust numeric representation. Such a structured description must also provide the ways of studying the correlations between both domains and take the advantages of matching audio with physical actions in order to open new ways of gestural synthesis.

Chapter 3 treats in detail our initial contributions. Most of the works dealing with the extraction of information related to instrumental gestures from audio have provided note-level description. In this sense, we first give a detailed description of the first contribution to this topic [MG05], where we dealt with a quantitative description of saxophone expressive recordings going beyond note-level. We established a schema for the description of gestures mainly in terms of dynamics. We considered four typologies of segments: attack, sustain, release and transition, based on their functionality and context in the score. However, we did not look at fundamental frequency modulations, just extracting information from an energy contour analysis. Moreover, the system in charge of the segmentation might result too specific for the case study, while it is based on a previous note segmentation. The following two contributions serve as an evaluation application for the former, showing the description to be consistent, at least for saxophone. After these two application contributions [RHM05] [MHRP06], we present our first work dealing with a quantitative description for fundamental frequency frequency contours [MBM06]. For this approach, fundamental frequency contours are modeled with no previous knowledge of the shapes. This is a step towards a generalized description of contours. Contours can be reconstructed from their parameterized versions. We test the consistency of the description by

training a classifier, in which we have considered three labels given by human observation. Again, we have based our procedure on a previous segmentation. Moreover, once we classify the articulations, we do not provide an appropriate specific description for each one of the classes, but just a decision based on the characterization. An interesting possibility is to give, in addition to the class, a numerical characterization of the execution of such class.

It is clear that the definition of gesture typologies, maybe following a hierarchical structure, must take into account context-related score constrains, as well as some instrument-specific constrains. Such a hierarchical definition of gestures may include several levels. A first may level consists on a classification due to their functionality in the musical task, or score context. This level would include attack, transition, release, sustain, etc. Then, in a second level, different types, attending to structural properties, of the upper level of description must be considered. For example, within the transition class, we may find (see Section 3.3.3) *scoop* or *portamento* sub-classes. Discovering typologies at this level from real performance data is also to be considered. The execution of the upper level classes in each particular situation would be quantitatively represented in a third level. Indeed, we plan to construct a framework based on such a hierarchical structure (see Section 4.3). Our approach is planned to work either for audio descriptors and for physical actions, or even a combination of both. We expect to be able to extract and classify much more information of gestures by also studying contours in the physical action domain, applied to the violin.

Within the audio analysis approach, we have started by studying energy and fundamental frequency contours as the two main parameters to define instrumental gestures. It is clear that some other high level perceptual descriptors are important for describing gestures, but it has been seen how some other high level descriptors may correlate with the two considered. Depending on the instrument, other perceptual parameters, such as roughness for the singing voice, become very important and will need to be attended. Although our first contributions worked separately for energy contour and pitch contour, further steps are thought for including the analysis of both (or even more, depending on the instrument and the importance of such parameter for performance) contours at the same time, using the same set of values of the two parameters for describing a particular gesture.

The most important issue is the assumption made on previous segmentation for the first contributions. For the first part of the proposed approaches we base our characterization study on a previous note-level and intra-note/inter-note level segmentation. We must definitely consider note segmentation as the base for a consistent alignment, but the question is whether to assume the segmentation problem as solved, or include it as a part of the characterization procedure. If it is to be included, it is clear that both processes will be consistent with each other and the overall performance will improve. A clear benefit from such a inclusion could be to segment, characterize and recognize gestures at once in the same framework or procedure. This means that the recognition of sequences of intra-note/inter-note segments (or other context-related instrumental gestures) lead to the recognition of note segments and thus to an automatic alignment to the score. Due to these reasons, we propose work in two directions, outlined next: (1) by assuming a previous segmentation of gestures and dealing with the quantitative description and classification of such segmented gestures; and (2) by building a framework in which a hierarchical structure of gestures, taking into account the context, is used to automatically segment and uniquely characterize gestures.

- **Quantitative description and classification of segmented gestures.** While this work aims at quantitatively describing instrumental gestures, we believe that classifying instrumental gestures is an important step to be done in order to provide a method for automatically giving appropriate characterizations. The first section of the proposed approaches (Section 4.2) proposes future directions in terms of quantitative description, and classification of segmented instrumental gestures.
- **Automatic segmentation and quantitative description.** The future directions for proposing a framework for automatically segmenting and quantitatively characterizing instrumental gestures is presented in Section 4.3. There, we expose the idea of defining a gesture grammar for music performance. In this gesture grammar, constituted by a dictionary and a language model, we understand gestures as 'words' a performer can 'say', depending on the score context, making an analogy to the spoken language. Following this approach, 'words' will be constituted by 'phonemes', representing the structural properties of gestures. The recognition and

characterization are carried out together by means of techniques similar to the ones that have successfully been applied in speech processing.

4.2 Quantitative description and classification of segmented gestures

In terms of quantitative description of gestures, we plan explore and get robust and compact representations that allow for posterior analysis and modeling. We believe in piece-wise representations (e.g Bézier spline modeling, see Appendix ??) because of their flexibility and also because of their potential relationship with the temporal characteristics of the contours. We briefly describe the two main approaches to be considered taken into account.

The first and more straightforward approach is to define a methodology for obtaining the quantitative description, by using an appropriate general parameterization (see Figure 4.1), used for all gestures of the same class. If we want the parameterization to be used for reconstructing the contours in a posterior synthesis stage, we think that it is not appropriate to use high order polynomials for representing complex contours due to the unclear relationship between each coefficient with the structural properties of the contours. This is one major reason for the intention to use piece-wise representation (as it has been already carried out in some other studies [Jen99a], [MG05], [MBM06]): small variations in the contour parameters must result into small variations of the contour itself. This parameterization may present a fixed number of parameters, or either a variable number of parameters (see Section 4.2.1). A previous human-based classification is needed for separating the gestures depending on their context or functionality in the score (gesture classes).

The second option is to adapt the contour parameterization component (or 'custom contour modeler' as it is depicted in Figure 4.2), based on a prior classification that determines how to characterize them in a posterior step. The ways for defining these classes from machine observation is briefly introduced in next Section. Thus, in this scheme, the first parameterization does not need to fulfill the requirement that the contours need to be able to be reconstructed from the extracted parameters, but just deciding the class to which the gesture belongs to,

Figure 4.1: Quantitative description of gestures

and so the most suited characterization method. Conversely, in the second step, it must be possible to reconstruct contours from the parameterizations. Additionally, these last parameterizations can also be expressed as deviations from the typical execution defined by the type or class they are belonging to: imagine that one of these classes is defined as those note transitions that present two perceptually audible inflections in the pitch contour, and the positions and signs of these inflections are expressed as deviations from the average values within the class.

Figure 4.2: Schematic representation of the two-step quantitative description of gestures

4.2.1 Automatic gesture classification

The automatic classification of gestures of the same type (contextual functionality) into different sub-types or executions can be performed by a typical supervised classification scheme that needs of pre-define typologies, or either by discovering patterns from real data. Both cases are introduced next.

Supervised classification

It is important to study the possible approaches to be applied for classifying gestures into pre-defined classes by using the quantitative description of the contours under study. These classes must be determined in advance by human reliable observation. This observation principles must respect the functionality of the gestures and the structural properties of the performance. The first step will be then to select the appropriate technique for representing and reconstructing contours, as well as the depth of approximation (perceptual studies must be carried out). We have some trust in combining Bézier splines and linear representations. Therefore, a well-established temporal relationship with the score has to be defined and taken into account in classification. This may -and surely will- vary depending on the instrument and the parameters into analysis. Different classifier instances are to be taken into account depending on the 'contextual' type of gesture. Here, we mean that the types here are determined by context, i.e., a gesture used for performing a transition between two successive notes (clear context) may be carried out following different patterns (classes into which classify). We have already carried out a study on singing voice performance following this approach, where we classified note-to-note transitions based on a quantitative description of fundamental frequency contour from which it is possible to reconstruct contours.

Pattern discovery

As it has been stated before, an interesting approach to be considered is to discover gesture typologies from real performance data. From a more scholastic musical point of view, gestures typologies may be already defined (e.g. legato and staccato articulations). However, particular styles of articulation may fall

out of the scope of such general classification, or either result into very different executions while included in the same pre-defined class. Thus, this fact motivates discovering patterns from real performance data. It is clear that one must start from a reliable segmentation, based on a set of contextual constrains. Such constrains should derive from a musical score context. Then, the proposed approach here is to use a set of unsupervised classification techniques (or clustering techniques) to automatically define and separate patterns into particular groups not defined a priori. We can see in Figure 4.3 a illustration of the possible steps to be carried out. The main stages are (1) contour parameterization and (2) contour clustering.

Figure 4.3: Schematic view of possible steps in gesture pattern discovery approach from real performance

The contour parameterization component will extract a compact set of parameters from which is possible to reconstruct the contours. Then, an unsupervised classifier is fed with such descriptions in order to find groupings that reveal different gesture typologies. For parameterizing contours, and depending on the nature of the description, some contours can be described by a small set of parameters, while others will need a larger set. This leads to investigate two different approaches for parameterizing contours: fixed number of parameters and variable number of parameters.

Fixed number of parameters. The first option is to extract a fixed number of parameters for each contour and feed the clustering component with them. Some

curve fitting techniques applied to the contour would give a more or less detailed description depending on the number of parameters. This option, while being more straightforward, presents a clear drawback: how to represent contours that present different complexities and different lengths by using the same number of parameters? Depending on how it is decided to parameterize the contours, it is possible to lose information in complex contours (too few parameters for the description), or either to introduce noisy information (too many parameters) for simple contours. A better approach is to use piece-wise description. In [MBM06] we have studied the classification (supervised classification) of different pitch note-to-note transitions in singing voice performance based on a fixed number of pieces. Although we obtained promising results, piece-wise fitting is a priori more adapted to a variable number of parameters. The main advantage of using a fixed number of parameters is the possibility of a general classification (clustering) step for every context-related typology of gesture.

Variable number of parameters. Conversely, depending on the complexity of the contour, the optimal number of parameters needed to represent it is going to vary. For classification purposes and using a classical classification scheme, feature vectors must present a fixed length. In this case, hierarchical classification techniques are going to be studied in order to pre-classify contours depending on the optimal number of parameters needed to represent them. This is illustrated in Figure 4.4, where each unsupervised classifier is fed with vectors of the same length, and decides how many parameters is needed, based on an approximation error function. It is probable that the same gesture typology can be described, depending on its complexity, by different number of parameters. This means that the output classes among different classifiers may coincide, thus featuring to a multi-space representation.

Classification of gestures via HMM

Other interesting approach for both discovering contour sequences, and also for performing supervised classification, is to group parameters of different Hidden Markov Models, each one fit with one different contour. These techniques have been already used in other areas (see for instance [Smy97] and [ASKP03]) for motion series, discovering typical paths in human movements. For each contour, we fit a HMM (presumably with continuous-density observation distributions)

Figure 4.4: Schematic view of possible steps in gesture pattern discovery approach from real performance

and obtain its parameter set λ . The number of states, number of mixtures models for the observation probabilities, and the HMM topology (left-to-right) are assigned same for all contours. This is schematically illustrated in Figure 4.5. This technique will enable to compute HMM parameter space distances using the model state transition, observation, and prior matrix differences [Smy97].

For the case of unsupervised clustering, several techniques are addressed in [Por04] on how to determine the optimal number of clusters (thus the optimal number of classes). By means of this technique, we allow for a *a priori* simpler classification scheme, with fixed length feature vectors. The length of these vectors is to be determined in advance, since it will be proportional to the number of states times the number of mixture models for state observation probabilities. Depending on the complexity of the contours to be classified, different lengths are to be tried. Moreover, normalization of the sequences time axis is avoided.

A clear drawback of this approach is the fact that although we may be able to discover clusters of gestures, it is not clear that we will be able to obtain, with the same modeling procedure, a quantitative description of each class which allows reconstructing a particular gesture, due to the *a priori* independency of each of the states of the HMMs with the structural pieces or properties of the gesture.

Figure 4.5: Illustration of the approach dealing with clustering of HMM parameters for discovering contour pattern

By *a posteriori* human observation, the correspondence between HMM states and parts or pieces of the contour is to be evaluated. This fact also implies that once a set of clusters or patterns of contours is discovered, a particular characterization method should be applied afterwards.

4.3 Towards a gesture grammar definition

Understanding music performance as the interpretation of a musical message and its transformation into musical sound by the selection and use of several available gestures, we believe that is feasible to treat instrumental gestures by applying similar approaches to which are taken in the field of speech processing. We propose here to apply techniques based on concatenated Hidden Markov Models (as in speech processing techniques) for representing temporal characteristics of studied contours, and build a gesture grammar based on these models. Words in speech correspond to gestures in music performance, while phonemes correspond to the micro-gestures or sub-segments that constitute the gestures. This analogy between speech and gesture in performance is represented in Figure 4.6.

In recent and successful speech processing techniques [Rab89], HHMs model the temporal evolution of spectral characteristics of sound. In our case, we will model the temporal evolution of contours of perceptual parameters or physical

Figure 4.6: Schematic view of the analogy between speech and music performance, comparing words with gestures.

actions. The aim is, as already introduced previously, to characterize quantitatively the shapes of such contours, and segment and recognize the sequences of gestures that the musician chose from a *a priori* defined set. Thus, we believe in the creation of a gesture grammar, adapted to each instrument and the parameters in study, that represent the use of gestures when performing a piece.

The basic elements of the grammar (see Figure 4.7) will be then a dictionary containing the model definition of every gesture to be considered (e.g. attacks, releases, etc.) and a 'language-like' model that defines, in a normal performance situation, either (1) which gesture is allowed to follow a particular gesture, or (2) a gesture transition probability. In the dictionary, there will also be reflected which micro-gestures or 'phonemes' are used to 'pronounce' each gesture or 'word'. Taking into account the score and the existing (defined) types of gestures and their possible executions (or sub-types of gestures), a set of possible sequences to be performed is obtained, from which the most probable one is going to be determined.

If we restrict the types of instrumental gestures to be limited in number, they can be seen as words from a set (namely a *dictionary*) from which musi-

Figure 4.7: Schematic illustration of the main elements involved in the definition of a gesture grammar for recognition and modeling instrumental gestures

cians choose the desired gesture at each moment, like humans also do with words in spoken language. This restriction is realistic when considering a particular context (e.g. a particular instrument and/or performer). General gestures typologies will be defined based on their context related to the score, and will be specific for each instrument. This can be carried out manually by human observation, or automatically by applying techniques as the ones described in previous Section 4.2.1 and Section 4.2.1 to manually segmented contours.

The use by the performer of each one of these words or gestures will not have sense at any moment, so a language model is needed for modeling the possible sequences of used gestures given a score to be performed, and assuming that the musician is respecting the score and is not making use of ornaments,

nor consolidations of notes. Several techniques can be tried in order to build this language model. Assuming (as it is the case) that we know in advance the score to be performed, a state machine like the one depicted in Figure 4.8 could serve for constructing all possible sequences of gestures fitting such score. Other probabilistic techniques like n-grams can be studied for such purpose. Of course, this for a particular case in which we consider that existing gestures are the ones represented, but it is general enough for representing the possible sequences of gestures in a typical attack-sustain-release-transition-vibrato-silence definition of excitation-continuous musical instrument performance. Therefore, the general problem to be solved here is to model how each one of these general gestures has been performed.

Figure 4.8: A possible performance state machine, where each state represent a possible gesture that the performer will utilize (note attack, note release, sustain, vibrato, transition, and silence)

We will consider now an example for the case of a score consisting on three consecutive notes, and the state machine represented in Figure 4.8. We must make some *a priori* assumptions (part of the language model):

- Each note coming from silence will present an attack segment at the start
- Each note going to a silence in the score silence will present a release segment at the end
- Vibrato and sustain may be present at most once within each note

- There will be a transition between each pair of notes

Some of the possible sentences or sequences of gestures allowed to perform such score will be then:

- ATTACK TRANSITION TRANSITION RELEASE
- ATTACK SUSTAIN TRANSITION TRANSITION RELEASE
- ATTACK VIBRATO TRANSITION RELEASE
- ATTACK SUSTAIN VIBRATO TRANSITION RELEASE
- ATTACK VIBRATO SUSTAIN TRANSITION TRANSITION RELEASE
- ATTACK TRANSITION SUSTAIN TRANSITION SUSTAIN RELEASE
- ATTACK TRANSITION VIBRATO TRANSITION RELEASE
- ATTACK SUSTAIN TRANSITION SUSTAIN TRANSITION RELEASE
- ATTACK SUSTAIN TRANSITION VIBRATO TRANSITION RELEASE

and so on...

The problem to solve is to find the sequence of gestures that best produced the extracted contours, and give a quantitative characterization of each one of them. If we considered more sub-types of any of the gestures (e.g. *attack1*, *attack2*), the possibilities would expand, but the idea is the same: recognize the gestures used at the same time as we characterize them, i.e. use the temporal characterization of the sequences for automatically segmenting and labeling the sequence of gestures carried out during performance.

As stated before, for modeling each of these gestures by quantitatively describing temporal contours of perceptual parameters or physical actions, we will consider them as successions or sequences of micro-gestures, reflecting the temporal evolution of the parameters taken into account. Each of these types of micro-gestures will share dynamic properties that describe their shape. An example of this is depicted in Figure 4.9, where the fundamental frequency contour of a 'scoop-up' transition between two notes shows three sub-segments (attending at the sign of the first derivative and its value) conforming the shape: *fall* part, *stable* part, and *rise* part. Other scoop-up transitions may present the same sequence of sub-segments but with different duration and derivative values, or

even present a modified structure¹ and being formed by a different sequence of sug-segments or micro-gestures. For the former, this would show variability in the execution, maybe depending on the context or on musician wishes. For the latter, another structure belonging to the same gesture typology can be considered as a 'synonym' or another allowed 'pronunciation' for that word. This idea, is depicted in Figure 4.7.

Figure 4.9: Waveform (Top) and Fundamental frequency contour (Bottom) of a scoop-up transition between two notes in singing voice performance. In this case, the gesture is defined by three successive 'micro-contours': *fall*, *stable*, and *rise*.

It is also important that each gesture definition contains a limited number of 'micro-gestures' (or 'phonemes' in its speech counterpart), since gestures are to be recognized based on the sequence sub-segments or 'micro-gestures'. This is problematic for the case of gestures like vibrato or tremolo, where a continuous oscillation of fundamental frequency or amplitude is carried out. In such case, it is not perceptually important how many oscillations occurred. For this type of

¹different structure but belonging to the same typology will happen for instance in the case of a scoop-up transition like the example, but not presenting the *stable* part.

gestures, there exist already several techniques used for detecting, characterizing and removing them as a preprocessed step [RDS⁺99].

4.3.1 A short experiment

Following part of the procedure described before, we have carried out a short experiment. In particular, we deal with automatic segmentation of gestures into micro-gestures, based on observing fundamental frequency contours of manually segmented transitions from singing voice performances. For doing so, we use concatenated Hidden Markov Models using the tool HTK [tSRt], intended for speech recognition, where one is able to define grammars and train models. Once we have carried out segmentation, we outline how to reconstruct contours by means of Bézier curve concatenation. We summarize here the most important aspects of the experiment on automatic segmentation, as well as some initial results.

Data preparation

For our experiment, we will try to automatically segment pitch contours of note-to-note transitions, extracted from real performance recordings, into homogeneous sub-segments of micro-gestures. We base our segmentation into the observation of fundamental frequency derivative. As a pre-processing step, the recordings have been analyzed, and several descriptors have been extracted. After being aligned to the target score, the whole performance is re-segmented into attack, sustain, release and transition segments. We collected 331 transitions transition segments, which will constitute our database.

Among the descriptors extracted from the whole performance, we focus on fundamental frequency contours. Fundamental frequency contours are extracted by from the values of pitch extractor based on auto-correlation analysis at a frame rate of 26,3 frames/second. A first step for preparing the contours is to remove oscillations due to vibrato and tremolo. This is carried out by means of studying zero-crossings of smoothed fundamental frequency derivatives [RDS⁺99]. Then, we must refill the gaps, as it can be seen in Figure 4.10, produced by unpitched consonants. For doing so, we compute slopes at the gap limits and render a constrained Bézier bicubic spline. This is detailed in Section 3.3.1. Finally, we

Figure 4.10: Waveform (top) and pitch contour (bottom) of a short excerpt from a singing voice performance recording. A discontinuity of the pitch contour due to the pronunciation of a unvoiced consonant is indicated by a red box. Intra-note and inter-note segments are segmented and indicated in green. Note boundaries are also segmented.

smooth fundamental frequency contours by means of a moving-average filter and extract first and second derivatives δf_0 and $\delta^2 f_0$ for being used in the training and recognition states. Values of the derivatives had to be compressed in order to avoid too high values that indeed decreased recognition rates. We applied \log_{10} to first derivative, and computed the second derivative directly from the compressed first derivative. Although very important for context characterization, we do not use yet the fundamental frequency value. In a later stage of recognition/classification, fundamental frequency value will be more important and taken into account when the relationship with the height of notes in the score is considered.

Grammar definition and data labeling

After observing the shape of the pitch contour of the transitions presents in the database, we decided for this little experiment to use a dictionary of three possible words ('rise', 'stable', and 'fall'), each one constituted just by one phoneme ('r', 's', and 'f') and a simple grammar able to describe the topology of the contours. We set the maximum length of possible sequences to four. With this information, we build a small dictionary in which each 'word' presents only a single pronunciation and this pronunciation is just the word itself. This is schematically represented in Figure 4.11. In Figure 4.10, it is also shown a real transition.

Figure 4.11: Schematic representation of the homogeneous segments of the pitch contours in a note-to-note transition

The task grammars can be written as an enumeration of possible sentences in case the problems to represent are simple, but more complex problems would need a graph-like representation. Other option is to get the grammar directly from manual annotations, since they are expected to be consistent with the problem. In this simple experiment, we have adopted both options, and no significant differences have been found out. The possible sequences of micro-gestures we used have been:

- STABLE

- RISE
- FALL
- STABLE RISE
- RISE FALL RISE
- RISE STABLE RISE
- FALL STABLE RISE
- FALL RISE
- FALL RISE STABLE RISE
- FALL RISE FALL RISE
- STABLE FALL
- RISE STABLE FALL
- FALL STABLE FALL
- FALL RISE FALL
- RISE FALL

Following the defined grammar, segmented transitions are labeled by hand into sequences of symbols, and the temporal limits of the points are approximately marked, as it is shown at the bottom of Figure 4.12, where a screenshot of the labeling tool (custom, written in Matlab) is shown. For the training we use compressed first and second derivatives of fundamental frequency contours. They are also shown at the top of the labeling tool.

Training and results

For training the model used for recognize the sub-segments or micro-gestures, we first prototyped HMMs for modeling each phoneme (in this case word). We have tried with two options. In the first one, we used single state models, while for the second option, we have used three state left-to-right models. For the second case, we allowed two new transitions between states, as it is illustrated in Figure 4.13. This has been decided because some sub-segments from the labeled data were short enough for lasting less than three frames.

We have initialized the model by using the manually labeled sequences of labels and the observable parameters and. No significant differences have been

Figure 4.12: Transition labeling tool, written in MATLAB

Figure 4.13: HMM models prototypes used in the experiment. Blue lines represent additional transitions for allowing short segments.

found by performing a flat start initialization (equal transition and emission probabilities) and an iterative Viterbi initialization [tSRt]. Then, we have trained the models using iterative Baum-Welch reestimation [Rab89]. Due to the small size of the database, we have used the same data in the training and recognition stages. Once the models have been trained, we use Viterbi decoding [Rab89] for recognizing the sequences of micro-gestures. We show the results in Table 4.1. We can see how the approach using three state models provided significantly better results. Higher recognition rates have been found in decoding single sub-

RECOGNITION RESULTS (%)	One state	Three state
Whole sequence	58.91	75.53
Single sub-segment	86.42	91.36
Accuracy	71.78	84.13

Table 4.1: Experiment recognition results for one state models and three state models.

segments or micro-gestures.

In Figure 4.14 we show the automatic segmentation results compared to the manual labels for two examples. While in the upper figure we can see that the labeled segments correspond to the output of the model, in the lower figure we see a bad recognition result. Nevertheless, we see how the recognized segment 'rise' does make sense by looking at the shape and derivative of the fundamental frequency, and we may have not segmented properly the contour. However, we must take into account that the number of phonemes we used here is just three, and it may not be sufficient for representing the temporal evolution of the contour.

Contour reconstruction

Once we have decoded the transition or gestures into micro-gestures, we can use the sub-segment limits for reconstructing the contours by means of concatenated a cubic Bézier curves (see Appendix B), one for each sub-segment or micro-gesture and respecting some continuity constraints. This is depicted in Figure 4.15, where the two attractors of the Bézier curves correspond to the inner control points of a the cubic curve. For the linear segments, we just set the inner control points at the same positions of the outer ones.

Conclusion

We have shown how to segment fundamental frequency contours of note-to-note transitions by using Hidden Markov Models in a meaningful manner, but we still need to extend the approach to the inclusion of any kind of instrumental gestures in the performance, letting the gestures (words) to be formed by more than one segment (phonemes), and thus recognizing and segmenting the contours into gestures and micro-gestures. In that case, a more complex grammar need to be

Figure 4.14: Two examples of good and bad recognition results

defined. Although the database used presents limited number of examples, it has shown the approach to be reliable. Micro-prosody due to phonetics has not been explicitly taken into account, but it is planned to study how the pronunciation of some consonants constrain contours.

Figure 4.15: Diagram of the process of automatic recognition of sub-segments and a posterior reconstruction fundamental frequency contours.

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Appendix A

Hidden Markov Models

In the beginning of the 20th century, Andrew A. Markov studied statistical properties of random processes and proposed a stochastic signal-model theory called the Hidden Markov Model (HMM). Hidden Markov Models were further developed and published in a series of papers by L. E. Baum and colleagues in the 1960s and the 1970s. A few decades later, HMMs became a popular mathematical tool used in various applications. Particularly, pattern-recognition based applications, such as speech recognition systems, have widely exploited the theory of HMMs. The following review of HMMs, not intending to be either extensive or detailed, is based on [Rab89], to which the author refers for further readings.

Markov chains are random-process state machines that consist of three elements: a finite set of states $S = \{s_1, s_2, \dots, s_k\}$, an initial state probability distribution, and a state-transition probability distribution. The set of states S defines the acceptable states of a random state sequence q_1, q_2, \dots, q_t in which $q_t \in S$ denotes a random state at time t . The initial state probability distribution assigns probabilities of the state machine to be in a certain state at time $t = 1$, i.e., $P(q : 1 = s_i)$ where $s_i \in S$. The state-transition probability distribution defines the probabilities for transitions from state s_i to state s_j during the random process, $P(q_t = s_j \mid q_{t-1} = s_i)$. Figure A.1 shows an example of a three-state Markov chain.

The mathematical power of Markov chains lies in the *first-order Markov assumption*, stating that the random state q_t conditionally depends only on the

Figure A.1: A Markov chain with a set of states $S = \{s_1, s_2, s_3\}$. The transition probabilities are indicated with directed arches. For example, $P(q_t = s_3 \mid q_{t-1} = s_2) = 0.1$. The initial state likelihood distribution could be $P(q_1 = s_1) = 0.5$, $P(q_1 = s_2) = 0.2$, and $P(q_1 = s_3) = 0.3$, for example.

preceding state q_{t-1} in a random-state sequence. This assumption may be formulated as follows [Pap84]:

$$P(q_t \mid q_1, q_2, \dots, q_{t-1}) = P(q_t \mid q_{t-1}) \quad (\text{A.1})$$

Furthermore, the conditional state dependency on two preceding states leads to the second-order Markov assumption, three to third-order Markov assumption, and so forth. In an alternative terminology, the state-probability dependency of $N - 1$ preceding states is also known as *N-gram approximation*.

Hidden Markov Models are an extension of Markov chains. At time t , the state machine is observed through an observation vector o_t of the machine. However, it is not possible to directly observe the state that emitted the observation. Therefore, the relationship between the random state q_t and the corresponding observation needs to be modelled with an observation likelihood distribution $P(o_t \mid q_t = s_i)$ where $s_i \in S$. This type of Markov chains are therefore called hidden, constituting a hidden Markov model.

As a result, the hidden Markov model can now be completely defined by the

following parameters:

1. The set of states $S = \{s_1, s_2, \dots, s_k\}$. The number of states is K .
2. The state-transition probabilities (for bigrams) $A = \{a_{i,j}$ for which

$$a_{i,j} = P(q_t = s_j \mid q_{t-1} = s_i), \quad i, j \in \{1, 2, \dots, K\} \quad (\text{A.2})$$

The matrix A satisfies

$$\sum_{1 \leq j \leq K} a_{ij} = 1 \quad \forall i \in \{1, 2, \dots, K\}, \quad (\text{A.3})$$

because the probabilities to move from a state to any state must sum unity. Analogous formulas can be written for trigrams as

$$a_{i,j} = P(q_t = s_j \mid q_{t-1} = s_h, q_{t-2} = s_i), \quad h, i, j \in \{1, 2, \dots, K\} \quad (\text{A.4})$$

and

$$\sum_{1 \leq j \leq K} a_{hij} = 1 \quad \forall h, i \in \{1, 2, \dots, K\}, \quad (\text{A.5})$$

3. The observation likelihood distribution $B = \{b_j(o_t)\}$ for each state, where

$$b_j(o_t) = P(o_t \mid q_t = s_j), \quad j \in \{1, 2, \dots, K\} \quad (\text{A.6})$$

denotes the likelihood of observing o_t given the state s_j .

4. The initial state probability distribution $\pi = \{\pi_i\}$, where

$$\pi_i = P(q_1 = s_i), \quad i \in \{1, 2, \dots, K\} \quad (\text{A.7})$$

denotes the *a priori* likelihood of the state s_i being the initial state, i.e., the actual state at time $t = 1$. Similarly, this satisfies

$$\sum_{1 \leq i \leq K} \pi_i = 1 \quad \forall i \in \{1, 2, \dots, K\}, \quad (\text{A.8})$$

The complete parameter set of a hidden Markov model is conventionally denoted by $\lambda = (A, B, \pi)$. As an important remark, the observation likelihood distribution is occasionally defined as an observation-symbol probability distribution in which continuous observation vectors o_t are replaced with discrete observation symbols. In that case, the observation symbols are typically included in the set of HMM parameters.

The HMM parameter set λ must be estimated so that the HMM models the process being analysed as accurate as possible. This is normally referred to as the *training process*. The parameter estimation is performed using the Baum-Welch algorithm (or the expectation-maximisation (EM) algorithm) which provides a maximum-likelihood estimate for the HMM parameters. The algorithm iteratively searches the parameter set that locally maximises the likelihood of observation sequences parameter set. In other words, the algorithm maximises the likelihood $P(O | \lambda)$ where O denotes all the observation sequences. The Baum-Welch algorithm is a well-known method, and it has been described by several authors, for example in [Rab89]. Once the parameters of the model have been estimated, it is used for recognising the state sequence that more likely generated each new observation sequence by means of the Viterbi algorithm [Rab89].

Appendix B

Bézier splines

B.1 Bézier curves

The following describes the mathematics for the so called *Bézier curve*. It is attributed and named after a French engineer, Pierre Bézier, who used them for the body design of the Renault car in the 1970's. They have since obtained dominance in the typesetting industry, as well as other computer graphic applications. The following review is based on some lecture notes from undergraduate courses [Bou00], [Jau03], and from [Sal06].

Consider $N + 1$ control points p_k , $k \in \{1, 2, \dots, K\}$ in n -dimensional space. The Bézier parametric curve function $B(u)$ is of the form

$$B(u) = \sum_{0 \leq k \leq N} p_k \frac{N!}{k!(N-k)!} u^k (1-u)^{N-k}, \quad 0 \leq u \leq 1 \quad (\text{B.1})$$

$B(u)$ is a continuous function in n -dimensional space defining the curve with $N + 1$ discrete control points $P_K = \{p_0, p_1, \dots, p_N\}$. $u = 0$ at the first control point ($k = 0$) and $u = 1$ at the last control point ($k = N$). This function presents the following properties:

- The curve in general does not pass through any of the control points except the first and last. From the formula, $B(0) = p_0$ and $B(1) = p_N$.
- The curve is always contained within the convex hull of the control points, so it never oscillates widely away from the control points.

- If there is only a control point p_0 , so $N = 0$, then $B(u) = P_0 \quad \forall u$.
- If there are only two control points p_0 and p_1 , the the formula reduces to a line segment between the two control points:

$$B(u) = \sum_{0 \leq k \leq 1} p_k \frac{N!}{k!(1-k)!} u^k (1-u)^{1-k} = p_0 + u(p_1 - p_0), \quad 0 \leq u \leq 1 \quad (\text{B.2})$$

- For the case of three control points, curves are usually called *quadratic Bézier curves*, and the formula reduces to:

$$B(u) = p_0(1-u)^2 + 2p_1u(1-u) + p_2u^2, \quad 0 \leq u \leq 1 \quad (\text{B.3})$$

An example showing a two-dimensional Bézier curve with three control points is shown in Figure B.1.

Figure B.1: Two-dimensional quadratic Bézier curve defined by the start and end points $p_1 = \{0.5, 1.5\}$ and $p_2 = \{2, 0.5\}$, and a single control point $b = \{3, 2.5\}$

- For the case of four control points, curves are usually called *cubic Bézier curves*, and the formula reduces to:

$$B(u) = p_0(1-u)^3 + 3p_1u(1-u)^2 + 3p_2u^2(1-u) + p_3u^3, \quad 0 \leq u \leq 1 \quad (\text{B.4})$$

An example showing a two-dimensional Bézier curve with four control points is shown in Figure B.2.

Figure B.2: Two-dimensional quadratic Bézier curve defined by the start and end points $p_1 = \{1, 1\}$ and $p_2 = \{2.5, 0.5\}$, and two control points $b = \{0.5, 2.5\}$ and $c = \{3, 2\}$

- The term

$$\frac{N!}{k!(N-k)!} u^k (1-u)^{N-k} \quad (\text{B.5})$$

is called *blending function* since it blends the control points to form a Bézier curve.

- The blending function is always a polynomial one degree less than the number of control points. Thus three control points results in a parabola, four control points a cubic curve, and so on.
- Closed curves can be generated by making the last control point the same as the first control point. First order continuity can be achieved by ensuring the tangent between the first two points and the last two points are the same.

B.2 Piecewise Bézier splines

As the number of control points increases it is necessary to have higher order polynomials and possibly higher factorials. It is common therefore to piece together small sections of Bézier curves to form a longer curve. This also helps control local conditions, because normally in Bézier curves, changing the position of one control point will affect the whole curve. Of course since the curve starts and ends at the first and last control point it is easy to physically match the sections. It is also possible to match the first derivative since the tangent at the ends is along the line between the two points at the end. Second order continuity is generally not possible.

Given four points p_0, p_1, p_2 , and p_3 , the definition of a cubic Bézier curve can be re-formulated as the classical form of a cubic polynomial:

$$B(u) = au^3 + bu^2 + cu + p_0 \quad (\text{B.6})$$

where u ranges from $u = 0$ (the start of the curve, p_0) to $u = 1$ (the end of the curve, p_3). The points a , b , and c are given as follows

$$c = 3(p_1 - p_0) \quad (\text{B.7})$$

$$b = 3(p_2 - p_1) - c \quad (\text{B.8})$$

$$a = p_3 - p_0 - c - b \tag{B.9}$$

We show now some cases of piecewise cubic Bézier splines, where each section correspond to a Bézier curve. Note that the end point of a section and the start point of the successive section coincide. The green markers correspond to p_0 and p_3 of each section. The blue markers correspond to p_1 and p_2 . The grey curve is the Bézier curve sampled 20 times, the samples are shown in red.

- **Example 1.** A single minimum piece of a piecewise Bézier curve. It is defined by four points, the curve passes through the two end points. The tangent at the end points is along the line to the middle two points. See Figure B.3.
- **Example 2.** Multiple curve pieces can be joined together to form longer continuous curves. The curve is made continuous by the setting the tangents the same at the join. Note that each piece of the curve is defined by u ranging from 0 to 1. See Figure B.4.
- **Example 3.** By changing the tangent points between two curve pieces, sharp transitions can be created. See Figure B.5.
- **Example 4.** The "strength" at the end points is controlled by the length of the tangent lines. The longer the line the more effect that tangent has. See Figure B.6.

For the case of concatenating cubic Bézier curves, it is possible to create a interpolating curve that passes through the given points by imposing some constrains, getting the name of *B-splines*. Subsequent reading on Bézier curve modeling and interpolation can be found in [Sal06].

Figure B.3: Simplest case of piecewise cubic Bézier spline formed by just a segment described by a cubic Bézier curve

Figure B.4: Piecewise cubic Bézier spline constructed by the junction of two cubic Bézier curve. Smooth transitions at the joins.

Figure B.5: Piecewise cubic Bézier spline constructed by the junction of two cubic Bézier curve. Sharp transition between pieces.

Figure B.6: Piecewise cubic Bézier spline constructed by the junction of two cubic Bézier curve. The longer the vectors corresponding to the inner control points, the more *strenght* at the joins.

Appendix C

Publications

- Hazan, A. Ramirez, R. **Maestre, E.** Perez, A. Pertusa, A. 2006.
'Modelling Expressive Performance: A Regression Tree Approach Based on Strongly Typed Genetic Programming'
Proceedings of 4th European Workshop on Evolutionary Music and Art; Budapest, Hungary
- **Maestre, E.** Bonada, J. Mayor, O. 2006.
'Modeling musical articulation gestures in singing voice performances'
Proceedings of 121st Convention of the Audio Engineering Society; San Francisco, CA, USA
- **Maestre, E.** Hazan, A. Ramirez, R. Perez, A. 2006.
'Using concatenative synthesis for expressive performance in jazz saxophone'
Proceedings of International Computer Music Conference 2006; New Orleans
- Ramirez, R. Hazan, A. **Maestre, E.** Serra, X. 2005.
'A Data Mining Approach to Expressive Music Performance Modeling'
Multimedia Data mining and Knowledge Discovery, Book Chapter, Springer-Verlag
- **Maestre, E.** Gómez, E. 2005.
'Automatic characterization of dynamics and articulation of expressive

monophonic recordings'

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- Ramirez, R. Hazan, A. **Maestre, E.** 2005.
'Intra-note Features Prediction Model for Jazz Saxophone Performance'
Proceedings of International Computer Music Conference 2005; Barcelona
- Ramirez, R. Hazan, A. Gómez, E. **Maestre, E.** Serra, X. 2005.
'Discovering Expressive Transformation Rules from Saxophone Jazz Performances'
Journal of New Music Research Vol.34 .4 319-330
- Ramirez, R. Hazan, A. Gómez, E. **Maestre, E.** 2004.
'Understanding expressive transformations in saxophone jazz performances using inductive machine learning'
Proceedings of Sound and Music Computing 04; Paris, France
- Ramirez, R. Hazan, A. Gómez, E. **Maestre, E.** 2004.
'A machine learning approach to expressive performance in jazz standards'
Proceedings of 10th International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining; Seattle, WA, USA